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**Behaviour of Reinforced Concrete Beams Strengthened by
Ultra-High Performance Concrete Overlays Reinforced
with Glass Fibre Polymer Bars**

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بِسْمِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

﴿ نَرْفَعُ دَرَجَاتٍ مِّنْ نَّشَأٍ ^{قَلْبًا} وَفَوْقَ كُلِّ

ذِي عِلْمٍ عَلِيمٌ ﴾

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Supervisor's Certification

This thesis entitled, "*Behaviour of Reinforced Concrete Beams Strengthened by Ultra-High Performance Concrete Overlays Reinforced with Glass Fibre Polymer Bars*", was prepared by "Hasan M. Abbas", under my supervision at the University of Babylon's Department of Civil Engineering, in partial fulfil the prerequisites for the Master of Science in Civil Engineering (Structural Engineering) degree.

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To our guardian, Imam Mahdi, my beloved

to the beloved Iraqi martyrs

Someone who stands by me is like my soul, praying for me every step of the way and helping me get through the tough times, For my dear mother.

For my life's pacemaker, the person I am unable to adequately express in words on paper. my wonderful father.

I sincerely thank my wonderful wife for her support;

I am grateful to my esteemed educators, the carriers of wisdom, for every letter you have helped me understand.

For every experience that gives me confidence and strengthens me.

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Contents

Abstract	x
List of Figures	xii
List of Tables.....	xvi
List of symbols	xviii
List of abbreviations	xix
CHAPTER 1 : INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Research statement	1
1.2 Aims and objectives of the research.....	4
1.3 Thesis outline	5
CHAPTER 2 : LITERATURE REVIEW	6
2.1 Introduction	6
2.2 Bond strength between UHPC and NC	6
2.3 RC beams strengthened by UHPC	9
2.4 Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP).....	27
2.5 Research originality and summary	29
CHAPTER 3 : EXPERIMENTAL WORK.....	31
3.1 Introduction	31
3.2 Beam design and test matrix	31
3.3 Materials characterization	34
3.3.1 Cement	34
3.3.2 Fine aggregate	34
3.3.3 Coarse aggregate	35
3.3.4 Silica fume	35
3.3.5 Micro steel fibre	36

3.3.6 Superplasticizer	36
3.3.7 Water	37
3.3.8 Steel reinforcement bars	37
3.3.9 Glass fibre reinforcement polymers (GFRP) bars	38
3.4 Formwork	38
3.5 Concrete.....	39
3.5.1 Mix design for NC	39
3.5.2 Mix design for UHPC	39
3.6 Mixing procedure	40
3.7 Strengthening scheme.....	42
3.8 Strain gauges	45
3.9 Test of hardened concrete-state properties.....	46
3.10 Specimen instrumentation and testing technique	46
3.10.1 Setup of specimens	47
3.10.2 Instrumentation of specimens	48
CHAPTER 4 : TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS	50
4.1 Introduction	50
4.2 Failure type and crack patterns.....	50
4.3 Ultimate load and load vs deflection response.....	58
4.3.1 Thickness of UHPC overlay	58
4.3.2 Reinforcement in UHPC overlay.....	59
4.3.3 Bond between UHPC and NC	61
4.4 Ductility.....	63
4.5 Energy of absorbed.....	65
4.6 Strains	66
4.6.1 NC strains.....	66
4.6.2 UHPC strains	67

4.6.3 Steel strains	69
4.6.4 GFRP strains	70
4.7 Concluding remarks	71
CHAPTER 5 : FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS	73
5.1 Introduction	73
5.1.1 Element type and geometry	73
5.1.2 Material Modelling	77
5.1.2.1 NC of RC beam.....	77
5.1.2.2 UHPC overlay	79
5.1.2.3 Model of steel and GFRP bars reinforcement	81
5.2 FE model validation	82
5.3 Parametric study	87
5.3.1 Steel reinforcement ratio	88
5.3.2 GFRP reinforcement ratio.....	89
5.3.3 CFRP reinforcement ratio	90
5.3.4 GFRP reinforcement length	91
5.3.5 NC Compression strength.....	91
5.4 Summary of results of Parametric study	92
5.5 Concluding remarks	96
CHAPTER 6 : ANALYTICAL MODEL.....	97
6.1 Introduction	97
6.2 Design guideline proposal	97
6.2.1 RC beam.....	97
6.2.2 RC beams with a UHPC overlay reinforced with GFRP	98
6.3 Previous studies	100
6.4 Predicted of experimental results	102
6.5 Predicted of FE results	106

6.6 Conclusion observations	108
CHAPTER 7 : CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	109
7.1 Introduction	109
7.2 Research conclusions	109
7.2.1 Experimental program	109
7.2.2 Numerical modelling	110
7.2.3 Analytical conclusion.....	111
7.3 Recommendations	112
REFERENCES	113
APPENDIX A – DESIGN OF BEAM.....	A-1
A-1 Design of beam.....	A-1
APPENDIX B – SUMMARY OF MATERIAL.....	B-1
B-1 Cement properties	B-1
B-2 Fine Aggregates properties	B-2
B-3 Coarse aggregates properties	B-2
B-4 GFRP properties.....	B-3
B-5 Epoxy properties	B-4
APPENDIX C – EXPERIMENTAL UHPC MIX	C-1
APPENDEX D- TEST OF HARDEN CONCRETE-STATE PROPERTIES	D-1
D-1 Cubical compression test	D-1
D-2 Splitting Tensile Test.....	D-2
D-3 Flexural tensile test (Modulus of Rupture).....	D-3

Abstract

Ultra-high-performance concrete (UHPC) has grown more and more in construction due to its superior mechanical properties and longer lifespan. Using UHPC overlays is an innovative way to update bridge decks and other structural elements, but there are drawbacks as well, like excessive thickness and localized cracking that increase the weight and cost of the structure. To improve and address these issues, this study proposes to add glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) bars to the UHPC overlay. An experimental campaign was conducted in this investigation to assess the performance of reinforced concrete (RC) beams strengthened in flexural using UHPC overlays reinforced with GFRP bars.

Twelve beams were used in this study; two were control beams (unstrengthened), and the other ten specimens were strengthened with UHPC overlay. The investigated parameters were thickness of UHPC layer, presence of GFRP bars, number and length of GFRP bars, and surface condition (two bond groups: the first was cast-in-place, and the second included both epoxy-only and epoxy-plus mechanical anchorages).

The ultimate load (P_u) and failure modes of beams were investigated in relation to plain overlays and overlays reinforced with GFRP bars. Localized cracking in UHPC was the main failure mode, and the use of plain overlays increased P_u by 30%–64% and 22%–39% in the first and second groups, respectively. The concrete beam structure showed flexural failures in the beams reinforced with GFRP overlays, which resulted in a significant increase in P_u (190%–258% and 267% in the first and second groups, respectively) when compared to the control beam. Furthermore, compared to the control beam, the addition of GFRP reinforcement greatly increased ductility, increasing it by 1.0 to 2.20 times in the first group and 5.79 times in the second.

In the study, the predicted-to-tested loads ratio of the ultimate load and ultimate deflection varied from 0.90 to 1.06 and 1.0 to 1.11, respectively, when comparing ABAQUS/Standard finite element (FE) predictions with experimental results. A 22% to 40% decrease in ultimate loading capacity was observed when the GFRP

ratio was lowered to 2.235% and 1.257% respectively. Three different steel reinforcement ratios (3.492%, 2.235%, and 1.257%) were applied in the UHPC overlay, resulting in a consistent linear enhancement in the P_u of the beam by 134%, 93%, and 57%, respectively, compared to the control beam. Additionally, when comparison is made with the beam strengthened by plain UHPC overlay, the ultimate load increased by 86%, 53%, and 25%, respectively. Using carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) bars as reinforcement to UHPC overlay caused a significant increase in the ultimate load compared to beams strengthened with GFRP reinforced UHPC overlay.

Ultimately, the utilization of normal concrete (NC) compression strength increased to 60 MPa led to a 10% increase in the ultimate load capacity of reinforced concrete (RC) beams when compared to the experimental value of 35 MPa. When the length of GFRP bars were reduced to 1500 mm (0.75 clear span of the beam), the ultimate load reduced by a negligible 5% compared to the beam strengthened with 2210 mm length GFRP bars.

An analytical model was utilized to establish a design guideline to predict the ultimate load capacity of beams incorporating GFRP-reinforced UHPC reinforcement. The developed regression equation for axial stress in glass fibre reinforced polymer bars demonstrated accurate predictions for ultimate load, exhibiting mean values of 1.00 and 0.97, with standard deviations of 0.05 and 0.03, respectively, when compared to experimental and FE study results.

List of Figures

Fig. (1-1) Common types of strengthening techniques.....	2
Fig. (2-1) Specimens with the different surface textures [19].	7
Fig. (2-2) Strength for each type of substrate surface [19].	8
Fig. (2-3) Shear connector type [20].	8
Fig. (2-4) Splitting and slant shear test results [21].	9
Fig. (2-5) Crack shape at failure: (a) RC beam without UHPC jacket; (b) beam without steel reinforcement with UHPC jacket; (c) RC beam with UHPC jacket, [2].	10
Fig. (2-6) Cross section of beams and reinforcement details and test structure [20]...	11
Fig. (2-7) Geometry of strengthened beams with UHPC in (a) the tensile side, (b) the compressive side, and (c) three side jacket [3].....	12
Fig. (2-8) Increment of the moment (a) at yield and (b) at failure (%) for the various examined techniques [3].....	13
Fig. (2-9) Numerical results for strengthened beams and for the initial beam (IB), (a) ST_UHPC_TS, (b) ST_UHPC_CS, and (c) ST_UHPC_3SJ [3].....	13
Fig. (2-10) Load-deflection curves of specimen beams [6].	14
Fig. (2-11) Load-displacement curves of models beams [5].....	16
Fig. (2-12) The process for preparing the beam surface and installing overlays is as follows: (A) Sandblasting the concrete surface for in-situ cast UHPC strengthening. (B) Employing epoxy adhesive for bonding and affixing UHPC strips for strengthening, [22].....	17
Fig. (2-13) Reinforcement of the strengthened beams with UHPC layers and UHPC layers and steel bars [23].	18
Fig. (2-14) Increase of the yield and the maximum load for the different thickness layer of UHPC and the different diameters of the steel bars [23].	19
Fig. (2-15) Geometry of the RC beam and details of reinforcement [24].....	19
Fig. (2-16) Geometrical details and reinforcement details of the RC beams [15].	21
Fig. (2-17) RC beams strengthened with CFRP-reinforced UHPC overlay [15].	22
Fig. (2-18) Geometric dimensions of specimens (a) RC beam (CB), (b) RUB, (c) PUB [25].	23
Fig. (2-19) Details of beams strengthening [27].	25

Fig. (2-20) Characteristic measurements of RC beam specimens: (a) Length details; (b) Transverse details [28].	26
Fig. (2-21) Stress-strain curve for SRFT and GFRP bars [30].	28
Fig. (3-1) Geometry and reinforcement details.	32
Fig. (3-2) Geometrical details and strengthening configurations(continue).	33
Fig. (3-3) Silica fume.	35
Fig. (3-4) Micro steel fibre.	36
Fig. (3-5) Steel reinforced for all specimens.	37
Fig. (3-6) Steel bar test.	37
Fig. (3-7) Plywood formwork.	39
Fig. (3-8) Casting NC for all specimens.	41
Fig. (3-9) Preparation of mix material.	41
Fig. (3-10) Procedure mixing of UHPC, (a) mix water and S.P. in a bowl, (b) combine sand, cement, and silica fume in a mixer, (c) add (a) in mixture, (d) Incorporate steel fibres into the blend, (e) Permit the blend to settle.	41
Fig. (3-11) Application of UHPC overlay for cast in place specimens.	43
Fig. (3-12) Application of the pre-cast UHPC laminate.	44
Fig. (3-13) Strain gauges applications.	45
Fig. (3-14) Location of strain gauges.	46
Fig. (3-15) Preparation specimens to conduct testing.	47
Fig. (3-16) Specimens setup in test machine.	48
Fig. (3-17) Instruments and tools used in the test procedure.	49
Fig. (4-1) Failure mode and crack pattern of control beam CB.	51
Fig. (4-2) Failure mode and crack patterned of beam B30.	52
Fig. (4-3) Failure mode and crack patterned of beam B50.	53
Fig. (4-4) Failure modes and crack patterns of beam B30G2 and B50G2.	54
Fig. (4-5) Crack patterned and failure mode of beams B30G3L1.5 and B50G3L1.5.	55
Fig. (4-6) Crack patterned and failure mode of beams B30E and B30E&A.	56
Fig. (4-7) Crack patterned and failure mode of beams B30G2E and B30G2E&A.	57
Fig. (4-8) Load-deflection at mid-span response for beams with various thickness of UHPC overlay.	59
Fig. (4-9) Load-deflection at mid-span response, examining the effects reinforcement ratio overlay.	61

Fig. (4-10) Load-deflection at mid-span response, examining the effects bonding overlay.	63
Fig. (4-11) Measured of ductility.	64
Fig. (4-12) Ductility value.	65
Fig. (4-13) Test beams energy absorption.	66
Fig. (4-14) Load-strain curves for compressive zone of NC.	67
Fig. (4-15) Load-strain curves of tensile UHPC overlay (continue).	68
Fig. (4-16) Load vs. steel strain curves of steel reinforcement.	70
Fig. (4-17) Load vs tensile strain of GFRP.	71
Fig. (5-1) FE modelling of beam, (A) Whole geometry, (B) Reinforced details and (C) Loading, support and element type modelling.	74
Fig. (5-2) Cohesive elements located in between the NC and UHPC overlay surfaces.	75
Fig. (5-3) Failure mode for different element sizes in beam B30.	76
Fig. (5-4) Response to load and deflection for B30 with different element sizes, (A) Ultimate load-element size curve and (B) mid-span deflection (corresponding to the ultimate load)- element size curve.	76
Fig. (5-5) Concrete beams with a material stress-strain model implemented, (A) Tensile stress-strain curve and (B) Compressive stress-strain curve, [50]	79
Fig. (5-6) The UHPC stress-strain relationship, (A) Compressive [54] and (B) Tensile model [49, 56], for UHPC with a steel fibre content of 2-3 vol.%.	81
Fig. (5-7) Relationship between tensile stress and strain in steel and GFRP reinforcement.	82
Fig. (5-8) Experimental and numerical load versus mid-span deflection comparison (continue).	83
Fig. (5-9) Comparison experimental specimens failure modes with numerical equivalents (continue).	85
Fig. (5-10) UHPC overlay-reinforced various steel rebar ratio; (A) load-deflection curve comparison between unstrengthened beam and plain overlay; (B) load and various steel rebar ratio.	88
Fig. (5-11) (A) Comparison of the load-deflection curves of unstrengthened beam and plain overlay with UHPC overlay-reinforced various GFRP rebar ratio; (B) load and various GFRP rebar ratio.	89

Fig. (5-12) (A) Examining the load-deflection curves of plain overlay and unstrengthened beams with UHPC overlay-reinforced CFRP rebar ratios; (B) comparing load and CFRP rebar ratios.	90
Fig. (5-13) Load-deflection curve comparison between B30G3L1.5FE, B30G2-FE and B30G2L1.5.	91
Fig. (5-14) The load and different compression strengths of an RC beam are compared in (A); the load-deflection curves are compared in (B).	92
Fig. (5-15) Response to load versus deflection in beams with strengthening schemes in parametric study, (A) CFRP reinforced in UHPC overlay, (B) GFRP reinforced in UHPC overlay, (C) Steel reinforced in UHPC overlay (continue).	94
Fig. (5-16) Load vs. rebar ratio for in beams with strengthening schemes in parametric study.	95
Fig. (6-1) Stress and strain diagram of RC beam.	98
Fig. (6-2) Stress and strain diagram of RC beam strengthened with reinforced UHPC overlay.	98
Fig. (6-3) Estimated load against comparing FE results using CFRP rebar's (A) tensile strength and (B) improved tensile strength (Eq. (6-4)) [4].	101
Fig. (6-4) Shear force and bending moment diagram for the tested beams.	102
Fig. (6-5) Predicted load using the GFRP rebar's tensile strength and the matching Exp. results, as shown in Eqs. (6-2) and (6-3).	104
Fig. (6-6) Predicted load using modified of the GFRP rebar's tensile stress.	106
Fig. (6-7) Compared the anticipated and FE findings following the modified FRP stress.	108

List of Tables

Table (2-1) Properties of models [5].	15
Table (2-2) Strengthening shapes of beams specimens [22].	16
Table (2-3) Experimental outcomes obtained from the beam testing [23].	18
Table (2-4) Details of beams of the experimental tested [24].	20
Table (2-5) Results of experimental test for specimens [15].	22
Table (2-6) Specimens description [25].	23
Table (2-7) Specifications for the beam specimens [27].	24
Table (2-8) Strengthening the RC beam specimen plans and the results of the experiments [28].	26
Table (2-9) Beams details [31].	28
Table (3-1) Details of all specimens.	32
Table (3-2) Silica fume characteristics [37].	35
Table (3-3) Characteristics of steel fibres that provided by the manufacturer (Jingjiang Hongtu Engineering Co. [40]).	36
Table (3-4) MasterGallium 54 characteristics according to manufacturer [42].	36
Table (3-5) Properties of steel bars reinforcement.	38
Table (3-6) Mix proportions for NC.	39
Table (3-7) Mix contents for UHPC.	40
Table (4-1) Experimental results summary.	51
Table (4-2) Evaluated of ductility of all specimens.	65
Table (5-1) Data required inputs for beam-UHPC overlay interface.	75
Table (5-2) The parameters of the material with damaged plasticity in concrete were utilized in FE modelling.	78
Table (5-3) Key results from FE and experiment are compared.	85
Table (5-4) Parametric study details.	88
Table (5-5) Results of parametric study.	92
Table (6-1) Compared predicted with experimental results by using Eqs. (6-2) and (6-3).	103
Table (6-2) Compared predicted with experimental results after modified GFRP stress.	105
Table (6-3) Compared predicted with FE results after modified FRP stress.	107

Table (B-1) Chemical analysis of the cement.	B-1
Table (B-2) Physical properties of the cement.	B-1
Table (B-3) Sieve analysis of fine aggregates.	B-2
Table (B-4) Physical and Chemical Properties of the Fine Aggregates.	B-2
Table (B-5) Sieve Analysis of Coarse Aggregates.	B-2
Table (B-6) Physical Properties and Sulfate Content of Coarse Aggregates.	B-2
Table (C-1) Trial UHPC Mix.	C-1
Table (D-1) Results of cube compressive strength test NC.	D-1
Table (D-2) Results of cube compressive strength test UHPC.	D-2
Table (D-3) Results of test of splitting tensile strength NC.	D-3
Table (D-4) Results of test of splitting tensile strength UHPC.	D-3
Table (D-5) Results of flexural tensile test (modulus of rupture) NC.	D-4
Table (D-6) Results of flexural tensile test (modulus of rupture) UHPC.	D-4

List of symbols

Symbol	Descriptions
δ_u	Mid-span ultimate deflection, (mm)
δ_y	Mid-span deflection corresponding to the first yielding of the Reinforcement, (mm)
ε	Strain
ε_o	Strain corresponding to f_c'
μ_c	Friction coefficient
σ_n	Normal strength (MPa)
τ_n	Shear strength (MPa)
\emptyset	Nominal Bar size, (mm)
μ	Ductility
ψ	Dilation angle, (degree)
ν	Poisson's ratio
ρ	The ratio of main reinforcement
P_{cr}	First cracking load, (kN)
P_u	Ultimate load, (kN)
A	Specimen cross-sectional area, (mm ²)
A_1	The area under the ascending part of load-deflection curve, (mm ²)
A_2	The area under the descending part of load-deflection curve, (mm ²)
C3D8R	An 8-node linear brick with reduced integration and hourglass control
T3D2	A 2-node linear 3-D truss
COH3D8	An 8-node three-dimensional cohesive element.
D_f	The diameter of micro steel fibre, (mm)
L_f	The length of micro steel fibre, (mm)
E_c	Modulus of elasticity of concrete, (GPa)
f'_c	Concrete compressive strength, (MPa)
f_{bo}/f_{co}	Ratio between the initial equilbiaxial compressive yield stress and the Initial uniaxial compressive yield stress
f_{ct}	Tensile strength of concrete, (MPa)
f_{cu}	Cube compressive strength, (MPa)
f_r	Modulus of rupture of concrete, (MPa)
L	Length of the cylinder, (mm)
W/C	Water to cement ratio

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ABAQUS	Finite element package
ACI	American Concrete Institute
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
CFRP	Carbon fibre reinforced polymer
e.g	For example
Eq.	Equation
et al.	And others
etc.	To the end
Exp.	Experimental
FE	Finite element
FRC	Fibre reinforced concrete
g	Gram
GFRP	Glass fibre reinforced polymer
GPa	Giga Pascal (equal to kN/mm^2 (10^3MPa))
HSC	High strength concrete
i.e	In other word
IQS	Iraqi Quality Standardization
kg	Kilogram
m	Meter
max.	Maximum
min.	Minute (s)
mm	Millimetre
MPa	Mega Pascal (MN/m^2)
NC	Normal concrete
No.	Number (issue)
SF	Silica fume
SPs	Superplasticizers
SSD	Saturated surface dry
T	Tension side
UHPC	Ultra-high performance concrete
Vol.	Volume

CHAPTER 1 : INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research statement

The members of concrete structures are disposed to weakening and deterioration. Consequently, these members may need to repair or strengthen due to aging e.g., environments causing corrosion of steel reinforcement, natural and human made extreme events such as earthquakes, vehicular impacts etc., or simply due to changes in design codes or changes in function of structure [1–4].

Some techniques have customarily been used for the repair and strengthening of concrete members such as concrete jacketing, steel jacketing, using intermediate supports, external pre-stressing, and bonding of steel plates Fig. (1-1) [5–7]. However, these methods can be considered as effective solutions in enhancing the serviceability and ultimate limit states of a structure, but, they have some disadvantages including increase in the member's weight and size, corrosion and failure of bonding in the steel plates [2,6,7]. Another common option is bonding fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composites [4,9] which has become commonly using in concrete structures during a short period of time [6,9]. However, the FRP material is characterized by its brittle nature, bonding challenges, weak behaviour under elevated temperatures and unsuccessful applications on moist surfaces or at low temperatures [7,10,11]. Based on the above discussions, seems that there are some limitations for using these strengthening techniques. Because of the above defects and limitations, which requires the use of an advanced technology of strengthening, commensurate with the architectural and constructional cases, there is a growing demand for the development of new strengthening techniques. One of these new strengthening techniques is using ultra high performance concrete (UHPC). The excellent performance of UHPC makes it suitable in restoration and strengthening works [11]. In addition, the low porosity of UHPC also provides extra protection for the damaged substrate when it is used as a repair material.

Fig. (1-1) Common types of strengthening techniques.

UHPC is a modern type of concrete produce in France in the 1990s with high characteristics including high workability, compressive strength, ductility, and resistance to environmental incidents [12]. UHPC is gradually started increasingly used in native and international structure markets in the construction of high rise structures, lengthy-span bridge girders, naval, flight, and defense structure applications because its high mechanical properties, and suitable long-term Behaviour, with superior mechanical properties including a compressive strength greater than 150 MPa, sustainable post-cracking tensile strength exceeding 5 MPa, high energy absorption capacity, and low permeability, shrinkage and creep [4,8,12-13].

CHAPTER 1.....INTRODUCTION

Perm and Murthy[14] in their study found a 30 % increase in the ultimate load capacity for reinforced concrete (RC) beams due to strengthening with cast in-situ UHPC overlays having (10–25) mm thickness. Martinola et al. [2] reported up to 116 % increase in the load capacity for RC beams strengthened with 40 mm thick UHPC jacket comparing with the unstrengthened RC beam. Taranslan et al. [6] proposed unreinforced UHPC laminates - which were attached to the beam bottom by only applying epoxy adhesives or combined steel anchorages with epoxy adhesives – the results show a 7%–22% increase in the ultimate load capacity. However, and due to use unreinforced UHPC layers, this significant improvement in ultimate load corresponded with a reduction in the ductility of the strengthened beams, attributed to the localization of failure caused by the brittle behaviour of UHPC.

Recently, few studies have used steel bars to reinforce the UHPC overlay and have resulted in significant increase in member strength, stiffness, and ductility [4] compared to unreinforced overlays. The contribution of steel rebars added to UHPC overlay is mostly enhancing the tensile stress–strain behaviour of the overlay, delaying or preventing the overlay macro-cracking and fracture, and acting as an additional reinforcement [15]. The main concerns when using reinforced UHPC overlays, typically 30 to 50 mm thick, are the high cost of UHPC material and the risk of corrosion on the steel reinforcement used in UHPC overlays due to inadequate cover when thin layers of UHPC were typically used.

Fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) composites offer many desirable properties including high strength, light weight, noncorrosive nature and good fatigue resistance [9,16,17]. Using FRP as an alternative reinforcement to UHPC layer will remove the corrosion problem fully and allows use of much thinner strengthening layers due to the fewer cover provision and higher tensile strength.

To the best of the author's knowledge, there are only a few existing studies on the flexural strengthening of RC members using UHPC overlays reinforced with FRP. However, there is a lack of studies specifically focusing on the flexural

strengthening of RC members with UHPC overlays reinforced with glass-FRP (GFRP) bars. This study aims to reduce the required UHPC thickness, increase the flexural load capacity, and subsequently enhance the effectiveness of the UHPC overlay. In addition, GFRP bars is the lowest cost compared to other composite material bars such as carbon-FRP [4]. Based on the aforementioned discussion, the aim of this research is to conduct experimental, numerical and analytical investigations to assess the effectiveness of UHPC overlays reinforced with GFRP rebars in enhancing the flexural strength of RC beams.

1.2 Aims and objectives of the research

Based on the statement provided, the research aims to evaluate the efficacy of UHPC overlays reinforced with GFRP bars in enhancing the flexural strength of RC beams. The focus is on reducing the thickness of the UHPC overlay. Additionally, the study will investigate the bond response between the UHPC overlay and RC beams by exploring various bonding techniques. Based on these aims, the detailed objectives of the research are as follows:

1. Experimentally assess the flexural performance of RC beams strengthened with UHPC overlays reinforced by GFRP bars.
2. Investigate the effect of reducing the thickness of the UHPC overlay on the flexural load capacity of RC beams.
3. Evaluate the bond behaviour between the UHPC overlay and the detached RC beams using different bonding techniques.
4. Study the effects of other different parameters on the overall behaviour of the RC beams strengthened with UHPC reinforced with GFRP bars including presence of GFRP bars and length of these bars.
5. Compare the experimental results with numerical and analytical models to validate their accuracy.

6. Provide insights and recommendations for the practical application of UHPC overlays reinforced with GFRP bars in strengthening RC beams in flexure.

These objectives will guide the research and help in addressing the specific aims of the study.

1.3 Thesis outline

The thesis is divided into the following seven chapters:

Chapter one presents a short-term introduction to the research with a statement of the aims and objectives of the research.

Chapter two offers a comprehensive literature review relevant to the research problem about the application of the UHPC with reinforced GFRP bars strengthening technique. The main aim of this chapter is to present and discuss the previous studies in this field to identify and explain the originality of this research.

Chapter three provides detailed analysis and description of the specimens that are tested, as well as the properties of the materials utilized in constructing these specimens.

Chapter four presents the experimental results and discuss these results in-depth.

Chapter Five discusses the validation of the numerical model with relevant experimental tests. This chapter also includes the results of certain parameters investigated using the validated numerical model.

Chapter six projects the flexural capacity of RC beams reinforced with UHPC. Then, the output of these formulas is contrasted with the findings of recent studies and additional research.

Chapter seven summarizes the main results and conclusions of the research with plans for possible future works.

CHAPTER 2 : LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter deals with previous research on the use of UHPC to strengthen concrete members including both reinforced and un-reinforced UHPC layers. In the beginning of this chapter, a review for the bond strength between UHPC and normal strength concrete (NC) is presented to have more understanding about this topic. After that, strengthening of NC beams with UHPC is discussed. However, and due to the lack of studies investigated strengthening of NC beams with UHPC layer reinforced with GFRP bars, the last section is discussed the use of GFRP bars as main reinforcement in RC beams. This can provide more understanding for the use of GFRP bars as reinforcement for UHPC which intends to be used in the current research.

2.2 Bond strength between UHPC and NC

Tayeh et al. in 2012[18] conducted an experimental work to measure the mechanical properties and porousness characteristics of the interface between NC substrate which represents old concrete structures and an overlay of UHPC as a repair material. Their results showed that the newly overlay UHPC achieves high bond strength and bonds efficiently with the NC substrate.

The bond strength in the inclined shear test was high strong, as the interfacial failure happened after the damage of the NC substrate. Splitting tensile test results showed that the failure mostly occurred in the NC substrate. This destined that UHPC bonded high strongly and efficiently with the NC substrate, resulting in composite that works almost monolithically.

The results of the rapid chloride permeability test (RCPT), gas and water permeability verify that UHPC has very low permeability characteristics due to high resistance against chloride penetration as well as gas and water permeation. Thus, the UHPC could form a good interfacial bond with the NC substrate and

CHAPTER 2..... LITERATURE REVIEW

improved the resistance of the NC substrate against the penetration of chloride and other aggressive fluids. Such attributes are expected to increase the service life of the repaired structures.

Tayeh et al. in 2013[19] studied the bond behaviour between NC which is the substrate and UHPC using slant shear test and splitting test to measure the efficiency of the bond strength in shear and indirect tension, respectively. In the study, the cubic compressive strength of the NC and UHPC were 45MPa and 170MPa respectively. The experimental parameter was the surface texture of the substrate. Five different forms of surface were made, that is (AC) as cast without roughening, (SB) sand blasting, (WB) wire brushing, (DH) drill holes and (GR) grooves surfaces, Fig. (2-1).

Fig. (2-1) Specimens with the different surface textures [19].

The bond strength between the UHPC and substrate depends on the surface handling of the substrate, as the surface treatment increases the bond strength increases. In this test, the sand blasted surface provided the higher tensile and shear strengths compared to other surface treatments, as shown in Fig. (2-2).

Fig. (2-2) Strength for each type of substrate surface [19].

Hussein and Amleh, in 2015 [20] investigated bonding methods between the NC to UHPC and high strength concrete (HSC) to UHPC using either shear stud connectors or dowels as shown in Fig. (2-3). Two 10 M bar dowels were connected 200 mm and 400 mm from the left support and used as a shear connector with the beams reinforced with dowels. For the beams reinforced with shear studs, three shear studs with 10 mm diameter and 100 MPa tensile strength were placed 150 mm spacing from the left support and used as a shear connector for the beams.

Fig. (2-3) Shear connector type [20].

The usage of dowels or shear studs did not significantly enhance the shear capacity of the composite beam.

AlHallaq et al. in 2017[21] studied standard slant shear and splitting tensile tests. The difference between surface roughness and bond strength in shear and indirect tension for different surfaces roughness has been evaluated. The NC surfaces

were roughened by mechanical wire brush, scratching using an electrical grinder, scabbling by a mechanical drill and as cast without roughening.

The results suggest that the bond strength increases when UHPC is utilized for both shear and tension applications when compared the bond between surface of NC to other NC surface. Specifically, when employing the scabbling technique, shear strength values are found to be 251.8% higher than those observed for the as-cast surface, while tension strength exhibits a 153% increase. Furthermore, UHPC possesses distinct advantages that make it suitable for repair and strengthening applications, including its ability to seamlessly integrate with existing concrete substrates during the addition of new concrete. Lastly, the findings indicated that tension strength is less influenced by the degree of surface roughness and more closely related to the strength of the repair material as shown in Fig. (2-4).

Fig. (2-4) Splitting and slant shear test results [21].

As summary, the bond between NC or HSC and UHPC can be affected by the roughness of NC or HSC. The use of sandblast or scabbling exhibits the best bond characteristics compared to other surfaces.

2.3 RC beams strengthened by UHPC

Martinola et al. in 2010[2] conducted an experimental work and numerical simulations to point out the effectiveness of the UHPC strengthening method in enhancing the response of RC beams, in both cases of strengthening and repair.

CHAPTER 2..... LITERATURE REVIEW

The usage of a 40 mm thick UHPC jacket on RC beams can increase the ultimate load of 2.15 times, and pre-damaged beam after repair same thick of UHPC case increase is about 1.90 times compared to control beam.

This technique was able to reduce the number of crack and width and hence the structure has higher durability, as shown in Fig. (2-5).

Fig. (2-5) Crack shape at failure: (a) RC beam without UHPC jacket; (b) beam without steel reinforcement with UHPC jacket; (c) RC beam with UHPC jacket, [2].

Hussein and Amleh, in 2015 [20] studied two groups of specimens (groups I and II) which were $(1284 \times 150 \times 300)$ mm ($L \times b \times h$) according to their composite material. Group I contains the control specimens (NC and HSC) while the beams in group II are the UHPC-NC&HSC composite beams. The length of the beams was designed to provide a left shear span to effective depth ratio of 3 in both groups as shown in Fig. (2-6). while, the right span was reinforced with enough stirrups to avoid shear failure in the left span. Four 30 M ($\text{Ø}30$ mm) longitudinal steel bars were used as the primary reinforcement and 15 M ($\text{Ø}16$ mm) steel bars were used as compression reinforcement.

The experimental results, the usage of a UHPC layer with 1.5% and 2% fibres volume contents at the tension zone of the NC beam significantly enhanced the flexural capacity by 54%, and 90% respectively.

Fig. (2-6) Cross section of beams and reinforcement details and test structure [20].

The deflection in central of the UHPC-NC/HSC composite beams was higher than the central deflection of the NC/HSC beams due to the high ductility of the composite when compared to the NC/HSC beams.

The maximum flexure load capacity of UHPC-NC beams between 402 and 520kN, which is 1.6 to 2.0 times higher than the flexure load capacity of NC beams. In addition, the UHPC-HSC beams maximum flexure load capacity between 413 and 522 kN which is 1.7 to 2.0 times than the flexure load capacity of HSC beams.

A series of RC beams with reinforcement percentages of 0.57%, 0.89% and 1.30% are strengthened with UHPC overlays with a thickness of 10, 15 and 20 mm prior subjected to flexural deterioration by **Prem and Murthy. 2016**[14]. The composite beams behaved homogenous under bending without deboning. The deterioration beams were able to retrieve its source flexural capacity with 10 mm overlay. The increase in load carrying ability of beams with 15 mm and 20 mm overlay was 24% and 35%, respectively for beams with reinforcement ratio

CHAPTER 2..... LITERATURE REVIEW

of 0.57%, 11.57% and 18.45% for 0.89% reinforcement ratio and 10.60% and 15.12% with 1.30% reinforcement ratio.

Lampropoulos et al. 2016[3] studied three UHPC configurations which were installing UHPC in tension side (ST_UHPC_TS), in compression side (ST_UHPC_CS) and in three sides (ST_UHPC_3SJ), as shown in Fig. (2-7). The dimension of specimens was (2200 × 150 × 250) mm (L × b × h). The maximum increase in moment was 167% and 178%, for M_y and M_u respectively for (ST_UHPC_3SJ) (M_y and M_u are yield and ultimate moments respectively) while for specimen (ST_UHPC_TS) was found equal to 29% and 31% for M_y and M_u respectively. The increase M_y and M_u in specimen (ST_UHPC_CS) were 29% and 28% respectively, as shown in Fig. (2-8).

Fig. (2-7) Geometry of strengthened beams with UHPC in (a) the tensile side, (b) the compressive side, and (c) three side jacket [3].

Fig. (2-8) Increment of the moment (a) at yield and (b) at failure (%) for the various examined techniques [3].

In numerical modelling, the results designate that the adding of UHPC layer in the tensile and in the compressive side had nearly the same effects to the yield and ultimate moment since an increment of about 30% was observed in both state in ultimate load. Adding a three side jacket resulted to significant increase in both yield and ultimate moments (160%–180%), as shown in Fig. (2-9).

Fig. (2-9) Numerical results for strengthened beams and for the initial beam (IB), (a) ST_UHPC_TS, (b) ST_UHPC_CS, and (c) ST_UHPC_3SJ [3].

Tanarlan et al. in 2017 [6] conducted an experimental work involving five specimens: the first one was kept un-strengthened (BEAM-1), the second and the third specimens were strengthened with a UHPC laminate having 3% steel fibre

CHAPTER 2..... LITERATURE REVIEW

which bonded with epoxy and anchorages between the two surfaces respectively (BEAM-2 and BEAM-3). The fourth and fifth specimens were strengthened with steel rebars-reinforced UHPC laminate with the same bonding of the previous specimens (BEAM-4 and BEAM-5).

The results showed that the increase in the ultimate load was 22% and 7% for specimen's BEAM-2 and BEAM-3 respectively. Using steel-reinforcement in the UHPC laminate resulted in an increase of lowest 73% in ultimate load, when compared to the corresponding un-reinforced specimen.

For the steel-reinforced UHPC laminates, the ultimate load of epoxy-bonded specimen was closed to the anchored one, the deflection at the ultimate load was 83% lower. Although the strength and the stiffness were increased by epoxy bonding UHPC laminate to the tension face, the behaviour was deteriorated and the specimen failed suddenly without showing any ductility is shown in Fig. (2-10).

Fig. (2-10) Load-deflection curves of specimen beams [6].

Tanarslan 2017[5] tested seven RC beams including one un-strengthened and 6 strengthened beams as listed in Table (2-1). The results showed that the use of

CHAPTER 2..... LITERATURE REVIEW

anchorage bonded UHPC laminate was provided very satisfactory results. The lowest increase of ultimate load was 32% and the highest one was 208% for the UHPC strengthened specimens as summarized in Table (2-1). In addition, adding internal steel-reinforcement to the laminate resulted in an increase of least 37% in ultimate load, when compared to the one recorded for non-reinforced specimens.

Table (2-1) Properties of models [5].

Specimen		Properties of UHPC laminates			Ultimate load capacity	
		Bonding procedure	Rebar in laminate	Additional application	P_u (kN)	Deflection ductility
BEAM-1	Control	-	-	-	43.21	5.28
BEAM-2	Strengthening	Epoxy	No	-	67.97 (57%)*	2.68
BEAM-3	Strengthening	Anchorage	No	-	57.23 (32%)	4.06
BEAM-4	Strengthening	Epoxy	Yes	-	93.26 (116%)	-
BEAM-5	Strengthening	Anchorage	Yes	-	89.23 (107%)	-
BEAM-6	Strengthening	Epoxy	Yes	CFRP U-jacketing	109.63 (154%)	2.40
BEAM-7	Strengthening	Anchorage	Yes	Laminate at compression	133 (208%)	1.76

*The percentage relative control beam.

Adding steel-reinforcement into the laminate is not enough to advance the behaviour of strengthened specimens since BEAM-4 was failed due to delamination of laminate and ductility stage that designates flexural behaviour was not noted for BEAM-5 due to concrete crushing in the compression zone Fig. (2-11).

Fig. (2-11) Load-displacement curves of models beams [5].

Al-Osta et al. 2017[22] studied three UHPC configurations namely as listed in Table (2-2): bottom (tension) side (BOTSJ), two sides Jacketing (2SJ) and three sides jacketing (3SJ). The dimension of specimens was (1600 × 150 × 250) mm (L × b × h). UHPC thickness in each configuration was 30 mm. Two methods were used to bond the UHPC with concrete beam: cast in place on sandblasting surface of concrete beams to an average depth of 2 mm and casting UHPC around it inside a mould, and the second technique bonding using epoxy adhesive to glued UHPC with concrete beams Fig. (2-12).

Table (2-2) Strengthening shapes of beams specimens [22].

Strengthening configurations (30mm thick of UHPC)		Ultimate load (kN)	Displacement at ultimate load (mm)	Failure type
Strengthening pattern	Specimen identification			
	RC-Control	70	19.10	Ductile
	RC-SB-BOT SJ	81	15.3.1	Ductile
	RC-SB-2 SJ	102	13.38	Ductile
	RC-SB-3 SJ	132	4.55	Brittle
	RC-EP-BOT SJ	75	12.13	Ductile
	RC-EP-2 SJ	95	15.7	Ductile
	RC-EP-3 SJ	129	4.35	Brittle

(A)

(B)

Fig. (2-12) The process for preparing the beam surface and installing overlays is as follows: (A) Sandblasting the concrete surface for in-situ cast UHPC strengthening. (B) Employing epoxy adhesive for bonding and affixing UHPC strips for strengthening, [22].

No significant change in the results for flexural testing of strengthened beams was observed based on differences in interface preparation method. However, sandblasting-UHPC casting in place method showed a general better performance as shown in Table (2-2).

Paschalis et al. in 2018 [23] conducted an experimental work for six RC beams which were constructed and used for the estimation of the performance of RC beams strengthened with UHPC layers. Two identical RC beams were used as reference beams, while other beams were strengthened with layers at the tensile

zone. For this investigation, two identical beams were strengthened with UHPC layers and two identical beams were strengthened with UHPC layers reinforced by steel bars as shown in Fig. (2-13).

Fig. (2-13) Reinforcement of the strengthened beams with UHPC layers and UHPC layers and steel bars [23].

The use of UHPC layers at the tensile zone of the RC beams resulted in a great increase in the stiffness of the RC beams and the formation of the cracks was delayed. Also, the load carrying capacity was somewhat increased.

The use of steel bars to the UHPC layer resulted in a large increase in the load carrying capacity of the strengthened beams. Thus, the average maximum load of the strengthened beams using UHPC layers and steel bars was increased by 89%, compared to the maximum load of the reference beams, as shown in Table (2-3).

Table (2-3) Experimental outcomes obtained from the beam testing [23].

Beam ID	Enhancement Method	Ultimate load (kN)
P _{average}	Control beam	54.6
U _{average}	UHPC layer	55.3 (1%)
UB _{average}	UHPC layer and reinforcing bars	103.5 (89%)

CHAPTER 2..... LITERATURE REVIEW

In numerical analysis, the amount of reinforcement within the layer plays a pivotal role in influencing the performance of the strengthened elements. Consequently, a higher load-carrying capacity can be obtained by increasing the quantity of reinforcement within the layer, even when using a thinner UHPC layer, as depicted in Fig. (2-14).

Fig. (2-14) Increase of the yield and the maximum load for the different thickness layer of UHPC and the different diameters of the steel bars [23].

Murthy et al. in 2018[24] conducted an experimental study in which the flexural behaviour of the strengthened RC beams were carried out. Three RC beams were tested until failure (reference beam) and the other beams were pre-loaded to different levels (70%, 80% & 90%). After pre-loaded, the beams were with a UHPC strip on the tension zone as shown in Fig. (2-15) and Table (2-4).

Fig. (2-15) Geometry of the RC beam and details of reinforcement [24].

Table (2-4) Details of beams of the experimental tested [24].

Type of Beam	Designation of beam	Type of Beam	Designation of beam	Strip thickness (mm)	Ultimate load (kN)
Control beam	CB1	/	/	/	69.62
	CB2				78.54
	CB5				87.91
Roughly 70% pre-loaded	A1	Roughly 70% pre-loaded and retrofitted	RA1	10	55.78
	A2		RA2	10	55.88
	A3		RA6	10	55.7
Roughly 80% pre-loaded	B1	Roughly 80% pre-loaded and retrofitted	RB1	10	68.65
	B2		RB2	10	67.87
	B3		RB3	5	68.21
	B5		RB5	8	66
	B6		RB6	10	68.24
	B7		RB7	12	67.25
	B8		RB8	15	68.38
Roughly 90% pre-loaded	C1	Roughly 90% pre-loaded and retrofitted	RC1	10	72.78
	C2		RC2	10	74.21
	C3		RC3	10	75.89

It was found that the load – deflection curves of all pre-loaded (70%, 80% and 90%) and strengthened RC beams were showed to be stiffer than the reference beams.

The ultimate load carrying ability of all pre-loaded (70%, 80% and 90%) and strengthened RC beams was a little higher than the ultimate load of reference beams. The selected thickness of UHSC strip (10 mm) was showed to be suitable for the pre-loaded (70%, 80% and 90%) and strengthened beams to regain their previous behaviour after to pre-loading and strengthened.

Kadhim et al. in 2022 [4] studied the efficacy of RC beams strengthened with CFRP-reinforced UHPC overlays through a robust finite element (FE) model. The model was validated against two existing experimental studies, resulting in excellent predictions for load–deflection and load-slip responses, cracking,

yielding, and ultimate loads as well as the failure modes. A parametric study, including 68 models, was conducted on five important parameters, which are reinforcement ratio of the beam and overlay, concrete compressive strength for the beam, overlay thickness and the bond between cast-in place overlay and the beam. In general, the method resulted in important increases in the ultimate load and ductility contrast to the control beam and those strengthened with unreinforced or steel-reinforced overlays and eradicated the overlay cracking failure. Changing the CFRP reinforcement ratio in the overlay for the strengthened beam results in a significant increase in ultimate load in range of 112–463%, compared to the control beam.

Kadhim et al. in 2023 [15] conducted an experimental work for six RC beams which were constructed and used for the estimation of the performance of RC beams strengthened with UHPC layers. The dimension of specimens was (1700×150 × 250) mm (L × b × h). One beam was reference (un-strengthened) and the other were strengthened in flexure with UHPC overlays, as shown in Figs. (2-16) and (2-17).

Fig. (2-16) Geometrical details and reinforcement details of the RC beams [15].

Fig. (2-17) RC beams strengthened with CFRP-reinforced UHPC overlay [15].

The results showed that the failure modes of specimens strengthened with unreinforced UHPC overlay with various thicknesses have a little effect, as shown in Table (2-5). Ultimate load increased significantly by 179% to 183% compared to the reference specimen, and by 157% to 159 % compared to plain UHPC with same thickness when UHPC reinforced with CFRP bars were applied.

Table (2-5) Results of experimental test for specimens [15].

Specimen ID	Ultimate load (p_u) kN	Increase in ultimate load %	Failure mode
B	90.3	--	Flexure
B30	97.8	8	Flexure
B50	100.1	11	Flexure
B30F2	251.8	179	Shear
B50F2	259.3	187	Shear
B50F3	255.6	183	Shear

CHAPTER 2..... LITERATURE REVIEW

Zhang et al. in 2023 [25] conducted an experimental work involving six specimens, with a dimension of specimens (2800 × 200 × 400) mm (L × b × h). Pre-load was applied on beams and stopped when the damage in the RC beam reached the target pre-damaged degrees, i.e. the maximum crack width of concrete reached 0.2 mm and 0.4 mm. The pre-damaged degrees were defined according to the maximum crack width limit for RC structure in the current specifications (JTG3362–2018) [26]. These beams were strengthened with UHPC casting as shown in Fig. (2-18) and Table (2-6).

Fig. (2-18) Geometric dimensions of specimens (a) RC beam (CB), (b) RUB, (c) PUB [25].

Table (2-6) Specimens description [25].

Specimen ID	Strengthening method	maximum pre-crack width (mm)	Effective pretention force (kN)
CB	/	/	/
RUB _{0.2}	RUHPC ⁽¹⁾	0.2	/
PUB _{0.2-1}	PUHPC ⁽²⁾	0.2	84.8
PUB _{0.2-2}	PUHPC	0.2	80.6
PUB _{0.4-1}	PUHPC	0.4	81.9
PUB _{0.4-2}	PUHPC	0.4	79.3

⁽¹⁾ Reinforced UHPC, ⁽²⁾ Pre-stressed UHPC

CHAPTER 2..... LITERATURE REVIEW

The results of the experimental program showed the failure mechanism in PUB involved the crushing of the compression concrete, which occurred after the yielding of the tensile steel bars. Notably, when compared to the unstrengthened RC control beam (CB) and the reinforced UHPC (RUHPC) strengthened control beam (RUB), PUB exhibited the formation of a single primary flexural crack at the ultimate limit state.

The cracking resistance and flexural capacity of PUB were significantly enhanced when compared to CB and RUB. The ductility index and energy absorption ductility index of PUB exhibited a decrease ranging from 9% to 24% and 1% to 26%, respectively, when compared to those of CB.

Ahmed et al. in 2023 [27] tested beams which had a rectangular cross-section of (100 × 300) mm (b × h) and a total length of 2000 mm. The test matrix was divided into three groups. The details of these groups are as shown in Table (2-7) and Fig. (2-19).

Table (2-7) Specifications for the beam specimens [27].

Group	Beam ID	UHPC length (mm)	UHPC thickness (mm)	Concrete cover	Explanation	Ultimate load (kN)
Contro I	CB	-	-	-	Control beam	72.16
Group I	B1-O-30	1000	30	Without	Strengthening length	102.02
	B1.2-O-30	1200	30	Without	Strengthening length	125.33
	B1.6-O-30	1600	30	Without	Strengthening length	140.98
Group II	B1-O-40	1200	40	Without	Thickness	131.73
	B1.2-O-40	1600	40	Without	Thickness	147.06
Group III	B1.6-W-30	1200	30	with	Existence of cover	99.81
	B1.6-W-30	1600	30	with	Existence of cover	100.08

Fig. (2-19) Details of beams strengthening [27].

The experimental results showed that increasing UHPC thickness of the layer, from 30 mm to 40 mm provided slight enhancement in the load capacity. Using a steel-reinforced UHPC layer at tension zone of the beam is an efficient technique that can develop load capacity at all cases, and enhance the stiffness. Increasing length of UHPC layer more than 1400 mm (about 70 % of the total beam length) did not show a noticeable effect on the behaviour of the strengthened beams.

Ahmed et al. in 2023[28] conducted an experimental work of four groups of beams. The dimensions of beams were (1600 × 140 × 230) mm (L × b × h) as shown in Fig. (2-20). The test structure consisted of three plans of a reinforced UHPC overlay with a thickness of 30 mm on the tension zone at the bottom section, two sides on the left and right of the section, and three sides, along with an additional control specimen, as indicated in Table (2-8).

The results of this study showed that the ultimate load of all three configurations was increased. One-side and two-side configurations showed almost equal increases in ultimate load, but the three-side configuration showed an increase of 51% over the two-side configuration as shown in Table (2-8).

Fig. (2-20) Characteristic measurements of RC beam specimens: (a) Length details; (b) Transverse details [28].

Table (2-8) Strengthening the RC beam specimen plans and the results of the experiments [28].

Strengthened shape	Damage (in relation to control beam failure load) degree (%)	Specimen ID	Ultimate load (kN)	Increase in ultimate load percentage (%)
	0	Control beam	87.2	---
	90	1S-90-01	100.2	14.9
	30	2S-30-01	122.7	40.7
		2S-30-02	127.0	45.6
	75	2S-75-01	112.5	29.0
		2S-75-02	111.8	28.2
	90	2S-90-01	109.9	26.0
		2S-90-02	110.3	26.5
	30	2S-30-03	141.5	62.3
		2S-30-04	151.5	73.7
	75	2S-75-03	127.8	46.6
		2S-75-04	125.4	43.8
	90	2S-90-03	119.3	36.8
		2S-90-04	124.7	43.0

2.4 Glass Fibre Reinforced Polymer (GFRP)

Kalpana and Subramanian, 2011 [29] revealed that the usage of GFRP bars instead of steel bars in concrete structure members is an important function due to non-corrosive environment. These materials possess a high tensile strength and low modulus of elasticity and show a linear stress–strain response up to the failure. The research emphasizes on gaining a vision into the behaviour of concrete beams reinforced with GFRP bars subjected to two-point loading system by changing the ranking of the concrete and diameter of the bar. The modes of failure and the crack width at each stage of loading were observed.

The GFRP bars embedded in the high strength concrete show a better performance compared to bars within the normal strength concrete, in terms of deflection and load-carrying capacity due to its high tensile strength.

El Zareefa, and El Madawy, 2018[30] studied using of GFRP bars instead of steel in reinforcing concrete structures, particularly for their lightness and non-corrosive characteristics. The research compared the flexural behaviour of beams reinforced with GFRP to the beams reinforced with steel reinforcement. A total of eighteen beams divided into six groups, each group consists of three matching beams were experimentally tested to study their flexural behaviour. Another objective for this study is to evaluate the existing methods used to estimation ductility of GFRP reinforced beams.

Generally, the behaviour of GFRP bars reinforced concrete beams exhibited lower ductility compared to steel-reinforced concrete beams as shown in Fig. (2-21). The ductile characteristics of GFRP-reinforced beams improved with higher GFRP reinforcement ratios, as indicated by the deformability factor. This suggests an increase in the deformation capacity before failure for beams reinforced with a higher GFRP reinforcement ratio.

CHAPTER 2..... LITERATURE REVIEW

The significant deformation observed in GFRP-reinforced beams can be attributed to the bars' ability to endure substantial strains before reaching their ultimate strength.

The deformability factor indicates that the tested GFRP-reinforced beams exhibit ductile behaviour, despite the presence of brittle materials like GFRP and concrete. This ductile behaviour can be attributed to the beams' high deformation capacity, which provides a significant margin of safety before reaching failure.

Fig. (2-21) Stress-strain curve for SRFT and GFRP bars [30].

Erfan et al. 2020[31] conducted experimental program contain of two groups of 300 mm depth, 150 mm width and span of 1600 mm as shown in Table (2-9).

Table (2-9) Beams details [31].

Series	Reinforcing type	Specimen Designation	Reinforcement Details		
			Tension Reinf.	Compression Reinf.	stirrups
Group 1 (NC)	Steel	B1 (NC)	2φ12	2φ10	φ8@145
	GFRP	B1-1	2φ8	2φ8	φ8@145
		B1-2	2φ10	2φ8	φ8@145
		B1-3	2φ12	2φ8	φ8@145
Group 11 (HSC)	Steel	B2(HSC)	2φ12	2φ8	φ8@145
	GFRP	B2-1	2φ8	2φ10	φ8@145
		B2-2	2φ10	2φ8	φ8@145
		B2-3	2φ12	2φ8	φ8@145

The ultimate loads of beams reinforced with GFRP bars exhibited an increase compared to those reinforced with steel bars. The increment in failure load ranged from 15% to 16% across the tested specimens. The study revealed that beams reinforced with steel bars exhibited the highest level of ductility compared to beams reinforced with GFRP. GFRP bars are employed to reduce the occurrence of cracks in both length and width.

2.5 Research originality and summary

Based on aforementioned review and to best of the author's knowledge, no study is found in which the RC beams strengthened with GFRP bars-reinforced UHPC overlay. The proposed study on the behaviour of UHPC overlays reinforced with GFRP bars for strengthening RC beams presents several original contributions to the field of structural engineering. The following aspects highlight the originality of this research:

1. Innovative strengthening approach: the use of UHPC overlays reinforced with GFRP bars for strengthening reinforced concrete beams is a unique approach that has not been extensively explored in the existing literature. While UHPC overlays and GFRP bars have individually been studied for their mechanical properties and durability, their combined application as a strengthening technique is relatively novel. This research aims to investigate the performance and behaviour of this innovative composite system.
2. Structural performance evaluation: the proposed study will comprehensively evaluate the behaviour of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with UHPC overlays reinforced with GFRP bars. It will assess key parameters such as load-carrying capacity, deflection, cracking behaviour, and failure modes. By conducting experimental tests, numerical simulations and analytical models, the research will provide valuable

CHAPTER 2..... LITERATURE REVIEW

insights into the structural performance of this composite strengthening system.

3. Interaction between UHPC overlay and NC substrate: the interaction between the UHPC overlay and NC substrate in the context of beam strengthening has received limited attention in previous research. This study aims to investigate the bond behaviour and load transfer mechanisms between the UHPC overlay and NC substrate.
4. Practical implications: the findings of this study will have practical implications for the engineering community and industry professionals involved in the rehabilitation and retrofitting of existing structures. By investigating the behaviour and performance of UHPC overlays reinforced with GFRP bars, the research outcomes can provide valuable insights for the effective and sustainable use of this strengthening technique (both UHPC and GFRP possess excellent resistance to corrosion, making them attractive options for enhancing the durability and service life of reinforced concrete structures.). This can contribute to the advancement of innovative and cost-effective solutions for infrastructure rehabilitation and retrofitting projects.

In summary, the originality of this research lies in its investigation of the behaviour RC beams strengthened with GFRP bars-reinforced UHPC overlay. By exploring this novel composite strengthening approach, the study aims to contribute to the knowledge and understanding of innovative techniques for improving the structural capacity and durability of existing concrete structure.

CHAPTER 3 : EXPERIMENTAL WORK

3.1 Introduction

The experimental program was conducted to investigate the behaviour of RC beams strengthened by UHPC reinforced with GFRP bars subjected to flexural load. The experimental campaign leveraged testing twelve RC beams under four-point load until failure. Two identical beams were used as control beams (unstrengthened), six beams were strengthened in flexure with field-cast UHPC overlays, and the remains were strengthened with pre-cast overlay UHPC (laminated).

The primary goals of this chapter are to outline and discuss the properties of the materials utilized in the present study. This includes cement, fine and coarse aggregates, steel fibre, steel reinforcements, UHPC and GFRP. The chapter will also provide comprehensive information about the test specimens, the strategies employed for strengthening, as well as the instrumentation and setup for testing.

The properties of the materials were evaluated through standardized tests adhering to the guidelines of the American Society for Testing and Material (ASTM) and Iraqi specifications. These tests were carried out at the Structural Engineering Laboratories of the University of Babylon. By describing these procedures and presenting the results, the chapter aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the material characteristics and the methodology employed in the study.

3.2 Beam design and test matrix

The dimensions of beams are $2250 \times 150 \times 250$ mm (length \times width \times depth) with a clear span between the supports of 2000 mm, Fig. (3-1). The choice of beam size was determined by several factors including the testing capabilities accessible to in Structural Engineering Laboratory at the University of Babylon, such as the load cell capacity and the hydraulic jack's limitations, as well as

budgetary considerations. This decision was also influenced by the precedence set by previous research studies, where similar beam sizes had been commonly utilized [26, 32]. The load was introduced using the four-point bending setup, wherein a constant moment region with a distance of 350 mm between the load points was maintained. The configuration resulted in a shear span-to-depth ratio of 3.78. The design of the beams was in accordance with the guidelines provided by the ACI 318–19 [33] code and were deliberately maximum allowable shear reinforcement and minimum allowable flexural reinforcement were intentionally chosen, to ensure flexural failure and facilitate evaluating the effectiveness of the strengthening system (**Appendix A**). The longitudinal reinforcement comprised six deformed steel bars with a diameter of 8 mm including, three bars used for tension and three for compression regions. The protective concrete cover for both the tensile and compressive reinforcements was consistently maintained at 20 mm on all sides. Closed-loop stirrups, each with a diameter of 8 mm and centre-to-centre spacing between these stirrups was consistently set at 110 mm, were employed as shear reinforcement along the entire length of the beam, as shown in Fig. (3-1). The test matrix included two control beams and ten strengthened beams as shown in Table (3-1) and Fig. (3-2).

Fig. (3-1) Geometry and reinforcement details.

Table (3-1) Details of all specimens.

Specimens ID	Parameter	Overlay Thickness (mm)	Bonding procedure	Overlay reinforcement details
CB1	Control	-	-	-
CB2		-	-	-
B30	Thickness	30	<i>cast in-situ</i>	-
B50		50	<i>cast in-situ</i>	-
B30G2	Reinforcement of UHPC	30	<i>cast in-situ</i>	2Ø10 mm GFRP
B50G2		50	<i>cast in-situ</i>	2Ø10 mm GFRP
B30G3L1.5 ⁽¹⁾	Length	30	<i>cast in-situ</i>	3Ø10 mm GFRP
B50G3L1.5		50	<i>cast in-situ</i>	3Ø10 mm GFRP
B30E	Bonding procedure	30	Epoxy ⁽²⁾	-
B30E&A		30	Epoxy & Anchorage	-
B30G2E		30	Epoxy	2Ø10 mm GFRP
B30G2E&A		30	Epoxy & Anchorage	2Ø10 mm GFRP

(1) the length of GFRP bars were reduced to 1500 mm (0.75 clear span of the beam).
 (2) When bonding procedure was epoxy or epoxy and anchorage, the UHPC overlay was precast and bonded to specimens after curing time.

Fig. (3-2) Geometrical details and strengthening configurations(continue).

Fig. (3-2) Geometrical details and strengthening configurations(continued).

3.3 Materials characterization

Standard tests from the ASTM as well as Iraqi Specification (IQS) were employed to characterize the chemical and physical properties of materials used in concrete batches.

3.3.1 Cement

Ordinary Portland cement (Type I) was a fundamental material used in this study for NC and Sulphate resisting Portland cement (Type V) for UHPC. The chemical and physical properties of these types of cement were evaluated through tests carried out in the Structural Engineering Laboratory at the University of Babylon. These tests were conducted according Iraqi Specification No.5/1984 [34]. Test results of chemical and physical properties are shown in **Appendix B (B-1)**.

3.3.2 Fine aggregate

Incorporating naturally occurring sand into NC mixtures is the primary focus, with particular emphasis on utilizing extremely fine sand particles measuring 0.6mm in size for UHPC blends. Additionally, it is noteworthy that the sieve

analysis outcomes for the natural sand align with the stipulated criteria outlined in **Appendix B (B-2)**, in accordance with Iraqi Specification No. 45/1984 [35].

3.3.3 Coarse aggregate

The gravel utilized in this study was sourced from the AL-Nibai region in Iraq. It underwent a thorough cleansing process with water and was subsequently allowed to air dry before deployment. It is worth noting that the gravel employed adheres to the specifications outlined in the IQS, No.45:1984 [35]. Detailed information regarding the grading and additional characteristics of this specific aggregate can be found in **Appendix B (B-3)**.

3.3.4 Silica fume

Silica fume MasterRoc MS 610 from BASF chemical company in the production of UHPC was used as shown in Fig. (3-3). Silica fume is a by-product of the production of silicon metal or ferrosilicon alloys and is known for its pozzolanic properties, which can enhance the performance of concrete. The utilization of silica fume in the production of UHPC yielded outcomes that align with the ASTM C1240-15 [36] standard specifications. The components of silica fume are detailed in Table (3-2).

Fig. (3-3) Silica fume.

Table (3-2) Silica fume characteristics [37] .

<i>Property</i>	<i>Specifications</i>
<i>Form</i>	<i>Powder</i>
<i>Color</i>	<i>Grey</i>
<i>Density</i>	<i>0.55 - 0.7 kg/l</i>
<i>Chloride content</i>	<i><0.1%</i>

3.3.5 Micro steel fibre

Micro steel fibres with a gold coating were used in the mixing of UHPC as shown in Fig. (3-4). The properties of this material are listed in Table (3-3). The steel fibres meet the requirements of the ASTM A820M-04 (2006) standard [38] [39].

Fig. (3-4) Micro steel fibre.

Table (3-3) Characteristics of steel fibres that provided by the manufacturer (Jingjiang Hongtu Engineering Co. [40]).

<i>Property</i>	<i>Specifications</i>
<i>Relative Density</i>	<i>7800 Kg/m³</i>
<i>Tensile Strength</i>	<i>>2800 MPa</i>
<i>Form</i>	<i>Straight</i>
<i>Average Length</i>	<i>13 mm</i>
<i>Diameter</i>	<i>0.2 mm</i>
<i>Aspect Ratio (L_f/D_f)</i>	<i>59</i>

3.3.6 Superplasticizer

In the mixing of UHPC, a high-range water reducer, known as MasterGlenium 54, was employed to enhance both the material's strength and its flow characteristics. It follows the (ASTM C494-15, 2015) [41] . Characteristics of the aforementioned material are indicated in Table (3-4) within the manufacturer's data sheet.

Table (3-4) MasterGallium 54 characteristics according to manufacturer [42] .

<i>Property</i>	<i>Specifications</i>
<i>Form</i>	<i>Whitish to straw coloured liquid</i>
<i>Relative density</i>	<i>1.07 gm/cm P3P@25PoPC</i>
<i>PH</i>	<i>5-8</i>

3.3.7 Water

Tap water was utilized for both the mixing and curing processes for all specimens in this study.

3.3.8 Steel reinforcement bars

Deformed steel bars 8 mm in diameter were used as reinforcement in all reinforced concrete beam as shown in Fig. (3-5). The tensile test (for three specimens of steel bars) was done at the Mechanical Engineering Laboratory at the University of Babylon according to (ASTM A615M-15, 2015 [43]) standard test (Fig. (3-6) and Table (3-5)).

Fig. (3-5) Steel reinforced for all specimens.

Fig. (3-6) Steel bar test.

Table (3-5) Properties of steel bars reinforcement.

<i>Specimen No.</i>	<i>Diameter of bar mm</i>	<i>Actual diameter mm</i>	<i>Yield stress MPa</i>	<i>Ultimate stress MPa</i>	<i>Grade 40</i>
<i>1</i>	8	7.92	358	486	<i>pass</i>
<i>2</i>	8	7.88	336	469	<i>pass</i>
<i>3</i>	8	7.95	341	478	<i>pass</i>
<i>Average</i>	8	7.91	345	477	<i>pass</i>

3.3.9 Glass fibre reinforcement polymers (GFRP) bars

GFRP bars with 10 mm diameter were used to reinforce UHPC overlay in some specimens, because of their high tensile strength, and excellent mechanical performance. Tensile strength and elastic modulus of GFRP bars used in this research as obtained from the manufacture (datasheet in **Appendix B (B-4)**) were 827 MPa and 46 GPa, respectively. The results of the data sheet were acceptable according to the standard specification (ASTM D7205M-06, 2011) [44].

3.4 Formwork

Plywood was used to make formwork for all specimens in this study with clear dimensions of 2250 mm×150 mm×250 mm, and a thickness of 12mm. Small steel nails were used to brace the pieces as shown in Fig. (3-7). Also several types and dimensions of steel moulds were used in the experimental program to determine the properties of hardened concrete, including: (a) Cylindrical Moulds 100×200 mm (diameter × height), were used to create cylindrical concrete specimens for tensile tests. (b) Prismatic moulds with dimensions of 100×100×400 mm for NC and 50×50×300 mm for UHPC, were employed to mould concrete specimens for flexural tests. (c) Cubical moulds mm, were used for moulding concrete specimens for compression tests. Six of these moulds had dimensions of 150×150×150 mm for NC, and the others have dimensions of 50×50×50 mm for UHPC.

Fig. (3-7) Plywood formwork.

3.5 Concrete

3.5.1 Mix design for NC

A specific concrete mixing process was used to produce the NC. Table (3-6) shows the mix proportions used in this study.

Table (3-6) Mix proportions for NC.

<i>Material</i>	<i>Mix proportion</i>
<i>Cement (kg/m³)</i>	<i>400</i>
<i>Fine aggregate (kg/m³)</i>	<i>850</i>
<i>coarse aggregate (kg/m³)</i>	<i>1050</i>
<i>S.P. (%)</i>	<i>4.3</i>
<i>Water (kg/m³)</i>	<i>125</i>
<i>γ_c (kg/m³)</i>	<i>2425</i>

3.5.2 Mix design for UHPC

The production of UHPC involved a series of trial mixtures to determine the ideal combination of components for achieving the desired strength and workability. Unfortunately, it is not possible to have a direct access to specific tables or figures due to the sensitivity of the UHPC mixture to factors such as mixing conditions, material quality, and quantities. As a result, over fifteen different trials were conducted, varying the UHPC mixture components, including cement type, sand, steel fibre, water-to-binder ratio, and superplasticizer-to-binder ratio, as shown in **Appendix C**.

CHAPTER 3..... EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Compression strength tests were performed on cubic specimens measuring $50 \times 50 \times 50$ mm at the age of 7 days, with a target strength requirement of over 100 MPa. Finally, the optimal materials and their respective quantities were identified, resulting in the desired compression strength, as detailed in Table (3-7).

Table (3-7) Mix contents for UHPC.

<i>Material</i>	<i>Mix proportion</i>
<i>Cement (Type V) (kg/m³)</i>	<i>950</i>
<i>Silica fume (kg/m³)</i>	<i>190</i>
<i>Fine sand (passes from sieve 0.6 mm) (kg/m³)</i>	<i>1050</i>
<i>Steel fibre (kg/m³)</i>	<i>157(2%)</i>
<i>Superplasticizer(MasterGlenium 54)/ binder (%)</i>	<i>3.5</i>
<i>Water/binder (%)</i>	<i>15</i>
<i>γ_c (kg/m³)</i>	<i>2518</i>

3.6 Mixing procedure

The mixing process was conducted using a central mixer for NC and all specimens were simultaneously cast, as depicted in Fig. (3-8). For UHPC, an electric pan mixer was employed in the structural laboratory of the College of Engineering at the University of Babylon. The mixer had a maximum capacity of 0.045 m^3 . Consequently, with this mixer, it was possible to cast two specimens during each mixing session, as the mixer's capacity allowed for 0.034 cubic meters of concrete. This quantity of concrete was sufficient for producing two specimens as well as a set of compressive strength cubes. To prepare the materials as specified in Table (3-7), but in a volume of 0.034 cubic meters, as illustrated in Fig. (3-9), follow these steps: a) Combine water and S.P. in a bowl. b) Place sand, cement, and silica fume into a mixer and mix thoroughly for approximately 3 minutes. c) Add the mixture from step (a) into the mixer. d) After 3 to 5 minutes from step (c), Manually introduce steel fibre in the form of small pieces into the mixer. e) Allow the mixture to settle, and once it has reached the desired consistency, it is ready for use, as depicted in Fig. (3-10).

Fig. (3-8) Casting NC for all specimens.

Fig. (3-9) Preparation of mix material.

Fig. (3-10) Procedure mixing of UHPC, (a) mix water and S.P. in a bowl, (b) combine sand, cement, and silica fume in a mixer, (c) add (a) in mixture, (d) Incorporate steel fibres into the blend, (e) Permit the blend to settle.

3.7 Strengthening scheme

The overlay system is applied to the underside of the beam. To ensure a robust bond between the overlay and the beam, the beam's surface is prepared by forming grooves at an approximate inclination of ± 45 degrees from the beam's longitudinal axis. These grooves are typically around 2 to 3 mm deep, as shown in Fig. (3-11a). Following the roughening process, it is essential to thoroughly clean the specimen's surface to ensure that it is free from any debris and is in a clean condition as shown in Fig. (3-11b). Six specimens of UHPC overlay were cast upside-down. Specimens B30 and B50 were cast using plain UHPC (as described in Table (3-1)). In contrast, specimens B30G2 and B50G2 were reinforced with GFRP bars ($2\text{Ø}10$ mm) having bars length equalled to the UHPC segment length. It should be noted that the length of UHPC segment was equal to the beam length for all strengthened beams. Specimens B30G3L1.5 and B50G3L1.5 were reinforced with $3\text{Ø}10$ mm GFRP bars but with length of GFRP bars 1.5 m. All these specimens were then left to cure for 28 days under room conditions, as shown in Fig. (3-11c). The remaining four specimens were strengthened using precast UHPC strips manufactured in plywood formwork with specific dimensions of $(2250 \times 150 \times 30)$ mm (length \times width \times thickness). Two of these strips were reinforced with GFRP bars ($2\text{Ø}10$ mm), while the other two strips were cast without any reinforcement. As previously detailed in Table (3-1), two strengthened beams (B30E and B30G2E) were produced by applying UHPC strips with only a layer of epoxy. Specifically, Sikadur 32 epoxy was used for bonding the UHPC strips in this study (the properties of this epoxy type are provided in **Appendix B (B-5)**).

The last two beams, B30E&A and B30G2E&A, were strengthened with UHPC strips bonded by epoxy and steel anchorages. 10 mm diameter steel anchorages were applied at intervals of 150 mm along the longitudinal direction of the beams, arranged in two rows, as depicted in Fig. (3-12).

CHAPTER 3..... EXPERIMENTAL WORK

Fig. (3-11) Application of UHPC overlay for cast in place specimens.

Fig. (3-12) Application of the pre-cast UHPC laminate.

3.8 Strain gauges

Strain gauges were attached to all beams to measure strains in specific points. Two strain gauges (5mm, 120Ω) were applied in tension reinforced in the mid-span and 100mm away from the mid-span of beams for all specimens as shown in Fig. (3-13) and Fig. (3-14). One stain gauge (30mm, 120Ω) was bonded on the compression region of NC of the mid-span of the beams as shown in Fig. (3-14). Also one strain gauge (10mm, 120Ω) was attached to UHPC at the tension region of the mid-span of the beams. Finally, a strain gauge (5mm, 120Ω) was applied at the mid length of the GFRP bars. To prepare the location for applying the strain gauges, it is necessary to carefully clean the area with acetone after removing the weak layer using sandpapers at the designated position.

Fig. (3-13) Strain gauges applications.

Fig. (3-14) Location of strain gauges.

3.9 Test of hardened concrete-state properties

A comprehensive testing process for evaluating the mechanical properties of different concrete mixtures (NC and UHPC), including compression tests, splitting tensile test and flexural tensile test. These tests help to ensure that the produced concrete meets the required standards for its intended use. These tests were conducted in the Structural Engineering Laboratories of the University of Babylon. The number of control samples and the process of calculation of each test type to determine the mechanical properties are shown in **Appendix D**.

3.10 Specimen instrumentation and testing technique

The procedure for preparing concrete specimens for testing involves several steps. After the curing process is complete for all specimens, the following steps are undertaken: (a) First, the specimens are cleaned to remove any dirt, surface imperfections, and unwanted debris from the concrete. (b) Next, the beams are

painted in white to facilitate the observation of cracking patterns and failure modes during testing. This is illustrated in Fig. (3-15)

Fig. (3-15) Preparation specimens to conduct testing.

3.10.1 Setup of specimens

The testing procedure included relocating the specimens onto the testing apparatus. The beam was oriented horizontally beneath the testing machine, with supports strategically positioned to create a 2000 mm clear span. To measure the deflection, LVDTs (Linear Variable Differential Transformers) were employed, with one positioned at the midpoint of the span and another at the support point. Additionally, a strain gauges were affixed to the concrete surface, along with the previously positioned threads on the rebar and GFRP bars, as depicted in Fig. (3-16).

Fig. (3-16) Specimens setup in test machine.

3.10.2 Instrumentation of specimens

This section delves into the equipment employed in the study. A data acquisition system comprising 8 channels for strain gauges, 4 channels for LVDTs to measure deflection, a load cell with a capacity of 200 kN to gauge the applied load on the specimens, and a hydraulic jack to apply loads to the specimens. Additionally, a computer was employed to display output data, execute calculations, and assist in the analysis, as shown in Fig. (3-17). The electronic system, vital for ensuring the validity of the test procedure and achieving precise details of structural members, was manufactured for this specific purpose.

Fig. (3-17) Instruments and tools used in the test procedure.

CHAPTER 4 : TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Introduction

In Chapter three, the preparation for the experimental program was presented. The results of the experimental program for twelve beams are summarized and discussed in this chapter. The chapter aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the findings, their implications, limitations, and potential applications. The chapter includes the results and discussion of the failure mode, ultimate load, cracking load, load-deflection response, ductility, absorbed energy and strain readings.

4.2 Failure type and crack patterns

The key result of the experimental work is summarized Table (4-1). In order to investigate the contribution of UHPC layer to the flexural response of beams, the specimens were designed to fail by flexure with (flexural capacity/shear capacity=4.0). The experiments showed that the two control beams (CB) failed by the conventional flexural mode as illustrated in Fig. (4-1). Initially, a flexural crack exhibited in the beam mid-span section at a load of $P = 18$ kN, followed by two cracks appeared under the load points. As the load increased, more cracks observed in the fixed moment zone and in the shear span. At load level ($P = 25$ kN), no new crack was developed but width of existing ones kept increasing. At a mid-span deflection ($\delta = 31.6$ mm), concrete at the compression side within the constant moment region started to fail and was completely crushed at ($\delta = 37.2$ mm).

CHAPTER 4 TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table (4-1) Experimental results summary.

Specimens ID	Load at first crack	Response ultimate		Increase in ultimate load %	Failure type
	P_{cr} (kN)	P_u (kN)	δ_u (mm)		
CB	18	32.12	37.2	-	F
B30	21	41.82	12.4	30	F + R
B50	35	52.73	4.1	64	F + R
B30G2	25	93.27	23.9	190	F + D
B50G2	26	106.94	28.6	233	F + D
B30G3L1.5	28	97.18	13.9	203	F + D + R
B50G3L1.5	29	114.83	16.7	258	F + D + R
B30E	30	39.21	32.7	22	F + R
B30E&A	28	44.64	3.4	39	F + R
B30G2E	33	117.82	65.9	267	F + R
B30G2E&A*	32	73.04	18.5	127	F + R

F: Flexural failure
D: Debonding of UHPC layer at mid-span
R: Rupture of UHPC layer.
*: Cut occurred in one of the GFRP bar during the process of drilling holes for steel anchorage.

Fig. (4-1) Failure mode and crack pattern of control beam CB.

CHAPTER 4 TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Comparable cracking behaviour was seen in beam B30 in which the cracks at the constant moment region and under the load points occurred at load level of 21 and 25 kN respectively. A closely horizontal crack was developed at the constant moment zone in the interface between NC and UHPC, at $P = 32$ kN, and spread sideways, (see Fig. (4-2)). At load level ($P = 35$ kN), localized vertical cracks developed in the overlay at mid-span and under the load points. At $P = 36$ kN, crack depths increased and reached about 85 % of the beam depth. Concurrently, the horizontal cracks spread and reached the load points. The pull out of the steel fibres from the UHPC matrix occurred at $P > 37$ kN. The flexural cracks in the beam mid-span for NC and overlay expanded rapidly, followed by crushing of concrete in the compression side which started to appear at ($\delta = 10.2$ mm) and completed at ($\delta = 12.4$ mm).

Fig. (4-2) Failure mode and crack patterned of beam B30.

Beam B50 observed similar cracking patterns to those in beam B30 (Fig. (4-3)). The first crack appeared at ($P = 35$ kN) at mid-span, followed by cracks at distance of 150 mm from loading points at ($P = 43$ kN). The flexural cracks extended to the overlay and developed more vertically into the beam. With load level of 50 kN, concrete started to crush in compression zone. The pull out of the

steel fibres from the UHPC matrix exhibited at load level more than 47 kN. The compression zone was crushed completely at ($\delta = 4.1$ mm). Similar failure mechanism has been also described in literature for beams strengthened with plain UHPC overlays [15] (e.g. B30, B50). Though, it is worthy to remark that in B30 and B50 beams, the NC-UHPC interface didn't exhibit any visible debonding.

Fig. (4-3) Failure mode and crack patterned of beam B50.

The beams strengthened by UHPC overlays reinforced with GFRP bars (B30G2, B50G2, B30G3L1.5 and B50G3L1.5), were exhibited patterns of cracks primarily resulted from flexure-related cracks. As shown in Fig. (4-4), the four beams presented extensive flexural cracks at the constant moment region and under point load and flexural-shear cracks within the shear span. The cracks extended down to the overlay and led to an audible continuous noise, likely due to the fibres being pulled out from the UHPC matrix. The fibres pull-out failure can easily be seen in Fig. (4-4). In beam B30G2 and B50G2, the mid-span flexural crack inside the beam and overlay expanded due to crashed in compression zone, followed a loud noise was heard after speared NC-UHPC interface debonding because sudden fracture steel reinforced and sudden drop in load.

Fig. (4-4) Failure modes and crack patterns of beam B30G2 and B50G2.

The beams (B30G3L1.5 and B50G3L1.5), faced the disengagement process due to the expansion of the horizontal cracks to the end of the length of the GFRP bars, which led to the failure of the beams due to the failure of the bonding and without the crashing of the compression zone and the occurrence of a sudden drop in loads, as shown in Fig. (4-5).

(A) B30G3L1.5

(B) B50G3L1.5

Fig. (4-5) Crack patterned and failure mode of beams B30G3L1.5 and B50G3L1.5.

Regarding the beams strengthened with epoxy bonded plain UHPC overlays strips (laminates) (B30E, B30E&A), the failure mode was different compared to the rest of the specimens discussed in the previous text. In beam B30E only one crack in the beam mid-span occurred as shown in Fig. (4-6), as it started at a load of 30 kN and continued to expand and extend to the compression zone until the specimen failed with one crack at a load of 39.21 kN. It is worthy to mention that in B30E beam; the UHPC-NC interface did not experience any visible debonding. It is important to emphasize that, in comparison to all other plain UHPC overlay

CHAPTER 4 TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

models, this beam has the longest loading period (highest deflection value at failure compared to other beams).

The B30E&A exhibited similar behaviour of beam B30 in terms of the cracks pattern and the type of failure as shown in Fig. (4-6). The cracks at the constant moment region and under the load points showed at P of 28 and 33 kN respectively. After that, cracks continued to expand and extend into the interior of the specimen until reached the compression side. Then the failure occurred at the load 44.64 kN, which corresponds to a deflection of ($\delta = 3.4$ mm). It should be mentioned that no debonding failure between NC and UHPC occurred in this beam.

Fig. (4-6) Crack patterned and failure mode of beams B30E and B30E&A.

CHAPTER 4 TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The beams strengthened by UHPC overlays reinforced with GFRP bar strips (laminates) and bonded with epoxy and mechanical anchorage (B30G2E, B30G2E&A) showed similar flexural cracks and failure mode to beams B30G2 and B50G2. The two beams presented extensive flexural cracks at the constant moment region and under load point and flexural-shear cracks within the shear span. The cracks extended down to the overlay and led to an audible continuous noise, likely due to the fibres being pulled out from the UHPC matrix. The fibres pull-out failure can easily be seen in Fig. (4-7). It is worthy to mention that the NC-UHPC interface of beam B30G2E&A didn't experience any visible cracking or debonding, while for beam B30G2E, even some minor cracks experienced in NC-UHPC interface but they did not extend to cause debonding. The beams were crashed in compression zone in end of the test with loads of 117.82 kN and 73.04 kN for beams B30G2E and B30G2E&A respectively.

Fig. (4-7) Crack patterned and failure mode of beams B30G2E and B30G2E&A.

4.3 Ultimate load and load vs deflection response

4.3.1 Thickness of UHPC overlay

The effects of UHPC overlay thickness is discussed in this section for both plain overlay and GFRP-reinforced overlay. For the former one, Fig. (4-8) (A) shows load against mid-span deflection response for beams CB, B30 and B50. The load-deflection curves of these beams are mostly bilinear with an insignificant variation in load after the yielding of longitudinal steel bars. Using plain UHPC overlays resulted in a reasonable increase in the beam's pre-yield stiffness, insignificant change of the load at first visible flexural crack, and 30% and 64 % increase in ultimate load (P_u) for beams B30 and B50 respectively, when compared to the control beam, as listed in Table (4-1).

Figure (4-8) (B), shows load-deflection curves for beams with various thicknesses of GFRP-reinforced UHPC overlay. When compared to the control beam, strengthened beams B30G2 and B50G2 showed a significant increase in stiffness accompanied by 190% and 233% increase in the ultimate load, respectively. When comparing the results for GFRP-reinforced UHPC overlay thicknesses ranging from 30 to 50 mm, it is evident that increasing the overlay thickness from 30 to 50 mm leads to a 14% increase in ultimate load capacity. This increase has negligible effects on the beam response.

(A)

(B)

Fig. (4-8) Load-deflection at mid-span response for beams with various thickness of UHPC overlay.

4.3.2 Reinforcement in UHPC overlay

In order to investigate the effect of configurations of GFRP reinforcement and for each thickness of UHPC overlay, two beams were tested under the same amount

CHAPTER 4 TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

of GFRP, but with different configurations. In the first one, which was discussed in the previous section, the number of GFRP bars were 2 with full length of the beam, while the UHPC overlay in the second one reinforce with three bars with a length of 1500mm as shown in Fig. (4-9).

When beam B30, which was strengthened with plain UHPC overlay ($h = 30$ mm) compared with beam B30G2, which was strengthened with UHPC overlay ($h = 30$ mm) reinforced with two GFRP bars with $\phi 10$ mm, the latter exhibits a significantly higher stiffness and ductility with a P_u value of 93.27 kN, 2.23 times that of the former and 2.90 times that of the beam CB as shown in Fig. (4-9) (A). Similar gains in stiffness and ultimate load were seen in beam B30G3L1.5, which its UHPC layer ($h = 30$ mm) was reinforced with $3\phi 10$ mm GFRP bars with a length of 1500mm in which P_u was 97.18 kN, 2.32 times that of beam B30, and 3.02 times that of the beam CB, as shown in Fig. (4-9) (A).

Similarly, beam B50 which was strengthened with plain overlay ($h = 50$ mm) compared with beam B50G2 which was strengthened with UHPC layer ($h = 50$ mm) reinforced by $2\phi 10$ mm GFRP bars, the latter shows a significantly higher stiffness and ultimate load with a P_u value of 106.94 kN, 2.03 times that of the former and 3.33 times that of the beam CB. Beam B50G3L1.5, which was strengthened with a reinforced GFRP reinforced UHPC overlay with a $3\phi 10$ mm, 1500mm length, and 50 mm h , demonstrated comparable increases in stiffness and ultimate load. This resulted in a P_u of 114.83 kN, 2.18 times that of beam B50 and 3.57 times that of beam CB, as shown in Fig. (4-9) (B). A plot of Fig. (4-9) (B) The load capacity of B50G3L1.5 increased by 7.4% in comparison to B50G2.

The superior tensile strength of GFRP bars helps the beams to resist the macro-crack opening in UHPC overlay. This resulted in a significant increase in the ultimate load and then improve entire response of the strengthened beams.

(A)

(B)

Fig. (4-9) Load-deflection at mid-span response, examining the effects reinforcement ratio overlay.

4.3.3 Bond between UHPC and NC

Fig. (4-10) shows the load–deflection curves for multiple beams, investigating the effects of bond between UHPC overlay and NC surface while holding

CHAPTER 4 TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

constant all other previous variables (GFRP reinforcement or thickness of UHPC overlay). Three distinct scenarios were examined: epoxy bonding, cast-in-situ bonding, and epoxy bonding combined with mechanical anchorage. This parameter was examined in both of the plain and GFRP-reinforced UHPC overlay scenarios for beams strengthened with a 30 mm UHPC layer.

Figure (4-10) (A) shows a comparison between the load-deflection responses for beams strengthened with plain UHPC overlay for various bonding technique. The first one (B30) has an ultimate load of 41.82 kN with $\delta = 12.4$ mm and the one strengthened with epoxy bonded UHPC layer (B30E) has an ultimate load of 39.21 kN with $\delta = 32.7$ mm. It seems that bonding the strengthening layer with epoxy provided better enhance in stiffness and ductility. This could be attributed to the good ability of epoxy to transfer stresses between the two layers. Regarding beam B30E&A, the ultimate load was 44.64 kN which is 6.7% increase when compared to B30, in addition to the good enhance in stiffness, as shown in Table (4-1).

The comparison between beams B30G2 and B30G2E in which the UHPC overlays were reinforced with GFRP bars is shown in Fig. Fig. (4-10) (B). The latter has an ultimate load of 117.82 kN, 1.26 times that of the former beam, and this is also regarded as a good improvement in stiffness and ductility. Regarding beam B30G2E&A, as indicated in Fig. (4-10) (B) and Table (4-1), the ultimate load was 73.04 kN, which is 21.7% less than that of beam B30G2 because a cut occurred in one of the GFRP bar during the process of drilling holes for steel anchorage.

In summary, when the NC surface was sufficiently roughened and epoxy adhesive was used, a significant increase in ductility and ultimate load can be observed.

Fig. (4-10) Load-deflection at mid-span response, examining the effects bonding overlay.

4.4 Ductility

The ability of a member to deform and absorb energy before failure is known as ductility, and it is a crucial property in structural engineering, especially in areas where earthquakes are common. Due to it permits significant structural deformations during an earthquake without compromising overall safety, ductility is a desirable property that can help prevent catastrophic structural collapses. In general, the ductility (μ) of a structural member, as a beam or slab, is often estimated by comparing two specific deflection values which are the deflection at the ultimate load (δ_u) and the deflection at first yielding of the flexure reinforcement (δ_y). as shown in Fig. (4-11) **Husain et al. 2017** [45].

Using strain gauges, the deflection at the yield point of the longitudinal steel reinforcement was measured carefully in this research. The results included the strain value at which the steel yields, which can be calculated by dividing the yield stress by the steel's elastic modulus ($\mu = f_y/E$). After that, a deflection reading can be obtained as shown in Table (4-2) and Fig. (4-11).

Fig. (4-11) Measured of ductility.

Fig. (4-12) illustrates the ductility index for beams strengthened with plain UHPC overlay. It can be seen from this figure that the ductility for strengthened beams is almost lower than that for the control beam. This is attributed to the brittle manner of UHPC, which enhance the ultimate load of the strengthened beams without providing an improvement to the ductility. Another reason related to the horizontal cracks occurred between UHPC and NC, which makes the UHPC behaving separately. For this reason, the beam strengthened with UHPC laminate bonded by epoxy provided greater ductility index compared to other beams. It should be mentioned here that B30E&A showed low value of ductility while no debonding occurred between UHPC overlay and NC beam. This is thought to be caused by that the mechanical anchorages caused an early crack in UHPC, which makes the failure of this layer earlier.

Table (4-2) Evaluated of ductility of all specimens.

Specimens ID	P_u (kN)	δ_u (mm)	δ_y (mm)	$\mu = \frac{\delta_u}{\delta_y}$
CB	32.12	37.2	9.28	4.0
B30	41.82	12.4	3.78	3.28
B50	52.73	4.1	3.21	1.28
B30G2*	93.27	23.9	---	---
B50G2*	106.94	28.6	---	---
B30G3 1.5*	97.18	13.9	---	---
B50G3 1.5*	114.83	16.7	---	---
B30E	39.21	32.7	4.89	6.69
B30E&A	44.64	3.4	2.23	1.54
B30G2E*	117.82	65.9	---	---
B30G2E&A*	73.04	18.47	---	---

* No yield in steel reinforcement was recorded for these specimens.

Fig. (4-12) Ductility value.

4.5 Energy of absorbed

Energy of absorbed (ψ) was used to represent ductility in this study by calculating area under the load–deflection curve **Husain et al. 2017** [45] and **Ebead et al. 2017**[46]. Figure (4-13) plots the amount of ψ for all tested beams. The beams, strengthened by plain UHPC overlay, exhibited a notable reduction in ψ , ranging from 1% to 87% when compared to the control beam (CB). This decrease can be attributed to its transition to a brittle behaviour. Beams

strengthened with GFRP-reinforced UHPC overlay which is cast in-situ provided in some cases significant increase in ψ , by 0 to 120% when compared to CB. Similarly, The beams strengthened with GFRP-reinforced UHPC overlay which is bonded with epoxy or epoxy and anchorage, resulted in a very significant increase in ψ , by 1% to 480% compared to CB.

Fig. (4-13) Test beams energy absorption.

4.6 Strains

The strains (ϵ) in beams at different locations, such as the NC compression zone (ϵ_{ncc}), the UHPC overlay tension zone (ϵ_{uhpc}), the steel reinforced in the bottom of the mid-span (ϵ_{st}), and the GFRP at the mid-span (ϵ_{gfrp}), were shared and discussed in this section.

4.6.1 NC strains

This strain gauge was positioned in the compression zone of the tested beams. The main aim of used this location to measure the compressive strain and to ensure whether the compression region of the tested beam reached the crushing

or not. Figure (4-14) shows the relationship between load and concrete strain for different tested beams. Under equivalent loads, the CB beam compressive strains were greater than those of beams B50 and B50G2. It seems from this figure that all strain values of the beams presented reached the curing value and the readings were agreed well with the visual investigations, which showed that all tested beams were failed with crushing the compression zone.

Fig. (4-14) Load-strain curves for compressive zone of NC.

4.6.2 UHPC strains

The UHPC load vs. strain curves were showed in Fig. (4-15). The ϵ_{uhpc} of the beams strengthened with plain overlay, like B30 and B50, and GFRP-reinforced overlay, like B30G2 and B50G2, were nearly the same before the overlay layer cracked. However, after the overlay layer cracked, the reading of strain gauges as shown in Fig. (4-15) (A) were quickly stopped because of overlay failure and losses of its extreme stiffness. The figure also showed that there are differences in the final value of the strain. This difference is attributed to location of the failure in the UHPC overlay. For instance, in beam B50, the rupture in UHPC

overlay occurred far away from the beam mid-span in which the strain gauge was positioned.

Similarly, Fig. (4-15) (B) shows tensile strain profile for UHPC overlay layer for beams B30G2, B50G2 and B30G3L1.5. Similar behaviour was observed for the presented beams. Again beam B30G3L1.5 showed lowest value of strain at failure. This obviously occurred because the failure in this beams was observed in the location where the GFRP bars were interrupted which is 750 mm away from the mid-span of the beam. Thus, it is expected to have a strain value lower than the maximum allowable strain in UHPC in the mid-span.

It is important to note here that the readings of the strain gauges in UHPC layer were agreed well with the previous research such as Kadhim et al. [15], Zhang et al. [25] and Ahmad et al. [28] in terms of that the curve is divided into three parts. Most of research studies conducted UHPC in tension showed that the behaviour of UHPC in tension divided into three parts including linear part which ended at the elastic state, the second part ended at the maximum stress and the last part which represents the cracked part.

Fig. (4-15) Load-strain curves of tensile UHPC overlay (continue).

Fig. (4-15) Load-strain curves of tensile UHPC overlay (continued).

4.6.3 Steel strains

Figure (4-16) plots the load versus strain curves in the steel bars. The strain in beams strengthened with both reinforced and plain UHPC overlays, like B30 and B50, and B30G2 and B50G2, increased almost linearly until the bars yielded. The strain increased more quickly when the concrete cracked. The yield load was raised by roughly 96% to 289% when the curves of the beams with CB in Fig. (4-16) (A) were compared. However, the failure was brittle, whereas the CB failure was ductile. The beams with GFRP reinforcement showed a significant decrease in ϵ_{st} when compared to plain overlay at the same load, as depicted in Fig. (4-16) (B). The sudden fracture that followed the overlay's debonding was not caused by steel yielding. The ϵ_{st} of the previous beams, B30G3L1.5 and B50G3L1.5, was also lower after cracking than that of B30G2 and B50G2, and it didn't reach the steel's yield because of failure overlay at the end length GFRP bars (see Fig. 4-16(C)).

Fig. (4-16) Load vs. steel strain curves of steel reinforcement.

4.6.4 GFRP strains

Fig. (4-17) plots the load vs GFRP bar's tensile strain (ϵ_{gfrp}) for the tested beams. For the beams strengthened by UHPC overlay with constant reinforced of two GFRP bars and different thickness (i.e. beam B30G2 and B50G2), the latter beam had lower tensile strain value (ϵ_{gfrp}) about 14%, as shown in Fig. (4-17). Similarly, for the beams B30G3L1.5 and B50G2L1.5, the results of the tests showed the same trend and behaviour compared to the beams that were mentioned at the beginning of this section. It should be mentioned that all tested beams did not show rupture in GFRP bars and this is agreed well with the readings of the strain gauges when the maximum strain in GFRP bars recorded in this research

was 0.014, while the ultimate strain of GFRP bars can estimate as $(827/46000=0.018$: ultimate stress/elastic modulus of GFRP).

Fig. (4-17) Load vs tensile strain of GFRP.

4.7 Concluding remarks

In general, the results of the twelve RC beams showed that the strengthening with UHPC provided an increase in ultimate load capacity and an enhancement in stiffness and ductility, and this can be summarized by the following points.

1. Compared to the control beam, the ultimate load of the plain UHPC overlay strengthened beams increased by 30% to 64%, and these beams are mainly susceptible to flexure failure after rupture of UHPC layer.
2. The increase in the load was 190%–267% when the beams were strengthened with GFRP reinforced UHPC overlay compared to the control beams. Following debonding, crushing of compression zone in NC happened in these beams.
3. As a result, when the thicknesses of the plain and reinforced overlays increased from 30 to 50 mm, the ultimate load increased by 26% and 15%, respectively. Furthermore, the reinforced overlay showed an increase in stiffness and ductility, while the plain overlay was more stiff than the control beam.

CHAPTER 4 TEST RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4. The impact of using three GFRP bars with a length of 1500 mm instead of two GFRP bars with the entire beam length caused 4% and 7% increase in the ultimate load compared to the equivalent thickness of UHPC layer of 30 and 50mm, respectively.

5. When comparing reinforced overlay to plain overlay, the strain on steel is reduced by roughly 14%.

6. When GFRP bars were used in the UHPC strengthened layer, no yielding in the longitudinal steel reinforcement was observed. This is reflected the ability of the strengthening scheme to carry most of the tensile stresses.

CHAPTER 5 : FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the finite element model created with ABAQUS 6.13-1 is explained, and this is the primary goal of the chapter. Also apart from validating it against published experimental results. The validated model offers a crucial instrument to broaden the examination of the behaviour of UHPC overlay reinforced concrete beams under flexural load without requiring costly, time-consuming, and repetitive testing.

Additionally, the objective of this chapter is to compare the experimental outcomes of the current study, which was detailed in Chapter 4, with the results produced from the numerical model utilizing ABAQUS/standard. Additionally, because of the experimental limitations program, a few variables omitted from the experimental testing will be explored in this chapter to offer further clarity.

In the experimental program explained in chapters three and four, twelve specimens were subjected to flexural loads for testing. A succinct explanation of the numerical model utilized in this simulation will be provided in the following subsection.

5.1.1 Element type and geometry

The FE model geometry as shown in Fig. (5-1), the effect tests were numerically simulated. Utilizing a reduced integration algorithm and Hourglass control, 8-noded brick elements (C3D8R) were used to model the RC beam, UHPC overlay, and steel plates positioned at loading and support locations are shown in Fig. (5-1). An axially-only stiffness 2-noded truss element (T3D2) was used to model the steel reinforcement and GRRP bars for the beam and overlay respectively. The steel reinforcement and GRRP bars did not slip from the RC beam or UHPC layer due to surface profile and adequate development lengths [4,6,23], and as a result, the "embedded region" approach was used to model the reinforcement as fully bonded. At the interface between the RC beam and UHPC overlay strip when

epoxy was used to bond these surfaces, did not experience any debonding failure, a similar perfect bond condition was applied using the "tie" constraint.

Contact elements (COH3D8) as shown in Fig. (5-2), and its properties are listed in Table (5-1), were used at the interface for cast-in-situ UHPC and rough surfaces preparation techniques at the RC beam and UHPC overlay because the experimental test in this study revealed partial debonding failure in these beams.

Fig. (5-1) FE modelling of beam, (A) Whole geometry, (B) Reinforced details and (C) Loading, support and element type modelling.

Fig. (5-2) Cohesive elements located in between the NC and UHPC overlay surfaces.

Table (5-1) Data required inputs for beam-UHPC overlay interface.

Characteristics [47][48]	τ_n (MPa)	σ_n (MPa)	μ_c	c (MPa)	δ^c (mm) [33]
Values	15.42	8.91	1.31	3.79	0.117

τ_n : shear strength; σ_n : normal strength; μ_c : friction coefficient; c : cohesion and δ^c : slip at compilation of debonding.

Specimen (B30) was the subject of a mesh sensitivity analysis examining four different element sizes: 50, 40, 30 and 20 mm. It was discovered that altering the element size had a discernible impact on both the failure mode as can be seen in Fig. (5-3) and the load and deflection response of the beam. The load and deflection response for the beam with element sizes of 20 and 30 mm was nearly identical. It reflected the corresponding experimental deflection amount the best, with only a small difference between them, as can be seen in Fig. (5-4). For this reason, the element size of 30 mm was used for all subsequent model parts (beam, overlay, GFRP bars and steel reinforcement) in order to reduce running time and disc space.

Fig. (5-3) Failure mode for different element sizes in beam B30.

Fig. (5-4) Response to load and deflection for B30 with different element sizes, (A) Ultimate load-element size curve and (B) mid-span deflection (corresponding to the ultimate load)- element size curve.

5.1.2 Material Modelling

5.1.2.1 NC of RC beam

The concrete damaged plasticity model was used to simulate the concrete beam because it can forecast the nonlinear stress-strain behaviour, crushing, and cracking of concrete [4,16,49]. The compressive strength ($f'c$), modulus of elasticity (E), Poisson's ratio (ν), dilation angle (ψ), shape factor (Kc), stress ratio (f_{bo}/f_{co}), and eccentricity (ϵ) are the inputs needed to define the concrete damaged plasticity model.

E was computed using the Eq. (5-1) from ACI [33], and ν_c was assumed as 0.2 in accordance with [17]. The other concrete damaged plasticity parameters' numerical values are shown in Table (5-2) along with the sources from which they were derived. The compressive stress-strain behaviour of the concrete was defined within the context of concrete damaged plasticity using the modified Kent and Park [50] model. For stresses up to $0.5 f'c$, the model assumes a linear response. After that, it assumes a nonlinear behaviour until the $f'c$ is reached. After that, the curve slopes down linearly in a manner that is dependent on the containment offered by the steel stirrups before plateauing at a stress of $0.2 f'c$. A linear elastic relation is used to model the tensile stress-strain behaviour up to the tensile strength (f_t), after which there is a linear drop to zero stress at a strain ten times that of f_t [46]. Furthermore, in accordance with Eq. (5-2), damage parameters (d_t, d_c) are added to define the stiffness degradation in the descending parts for the compressive and tensile stress-strain curves, respectively:

$$E = 4700 \sqrt{f'c} \tag{5-1}$$

$$d_t \text{ or } d_c = 1 - \frac{\sigma}{f} \tag{5-2}$$

where f represents the material's tensile or compressive strengths ($f_t, f'c$) and σ is the actual tensile or compressive stress. The range of numerical values for d_t

and d_c is $\underline{0}$ (undamaged) to $\underline{1}$ (final damaged), with intermediate values denoting different degrees of partial damage.

ACI [33] formula $[f_t = 0.62\sqrt{f'c}]$ is used to determine the peak stress, which in tension corresponds to the concrete's tensile strength. Fig. (5-5) (A) shows the ultimate strain, which is 50 times the strain at cracking.

The compressive-strain curves for two sections of the model, illustrated in Fig. (5-5) (B), can be identified: a linear descending line from failure onward and a parabolic ascending curve up to the concrete strength ($f'c$). Up to a stress of $0.5 f'c$, the concrete is thought to be linear in the first section (region AB in Fig. (5-5) (B)). Eq. (5-3) relates the concrete strain (ϵ_c) to the concrete stress (fc) in the following region [line BC in Fig. (5-5) (B)].

$$f_c = f'c \left[2 \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_0} \right) - \left(\frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_0} \right)^2 \right] \tag{5-3}$$

the strain at $f'c$ is denoted by ϵ_0 , which can be computed as $\epsilon_0 = \frac{2f'c}{E_c}$ [50].

The $fc - \epsilon_c$ relation for region concrete damage in the second portion [i.e. at $\epsilon_0 \leq \epsilon_c \leq \epsilon_{20c}$] is linear Fig. (5-5) (B), and its slope is determined by the confinement ratio, contingent upon the stirrup details specified below (Eq. (5-4):

$$f_c = f'c [1 - Z(\epsilon_c - \epsilon_0)] \tag{5-4}$$

Where $Z = \frac{0.5}{\epsilon_{50u} + \epsilon_{50h} - \epsilon_{c0}}$, $\epsilon_{50u} = \frac{30 + 29f'c}{145f'c - 1000}$, $\epsilon_{50h} = \frac{3}{4} \dot{\rho} \sqrt{\frac{\dot{b}}{S}}$, $\dot{\rho} = \frac{2(\dot{b} + \dot{d})\dot{A}_s}{\dot{b} \dot{d} S}$

S is the centre-to-centre spacing of the hoops, \dot{A}_s is the cross-sectional area of the hoop bar, and \dot{b} and \dot{d} are the width and depth of the confined core, respectively.

Table (5-2) The parameters of the material with damaged plasticity in concrete were utilized in FE modelling.

Concrete type	Angle of dilation (ψ) in degrees	Eccentricity (ϵ)	Shape factor (K_c)	Stress ratio (f_{bo}/f_{co})
NC [51]	40	0.1	0.667	1.16
UHPC [52]	56	0.1	0.66	1.1

Fig. (5-5) Concrete beams with a material stress-strain model implemented, (A) Tensile stress-strain curve and (B) Compressive stress-strain curve, [50]

5.1.2.2 UHPC overlay

For the overlay, a macro-level material model that also used the concrete damaged plasticity model for numerical implementation. In this model, the fibres are assumed to be uniformly distributed in the cementitious matrix and are simulated indirectly by smearing their effects into the tensile and compressive properties of the UHPC. While some studies examining the fibre-matrix bond for small-scale specimens use a more refined approach, where the fibres are modelled as a discrete reinforcement [4,53], for large-scale specimens, this approach is computationally inefficient and requires a large number of elements and very long run times.

According to the previous researches [4,54,55], the UHPC elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio within the concrete damaged plasticity model were determined to be ($E = 3840 \sqrt{f'_c}$) and 0.18, respectively. Table (5-2) contains a list of additional parameters that define the concrete damaged plasticity model for UHPC along with the references from which they were derived. This study uses by [54] model to define the compressive stress-strain response of UHPC.

In this study, the stress-strain model in tension was taken from modulus of rupture in the experimental tests, Fig. (5-6) displays the tensile and compressive

stress-strain curves for the UHPC overlay graphically. According to the model, the behaviour is assumed to be linear up to $0.5 f'c$, then nonlinear at $f'c$, and finally a final descending line with a steep slope that mimics the brittle failure that UHPC usually encounters in compression. Previous study[54] formulation was used to introduce the stress-strain response of UHPC in compression; Fig. (5-6) (A) illustrates this.

The elastic region in this stress-strain model is represented by the first part (segment A-B in Fig. (5-6) (A)), which is defined by the elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio as previously mentioned. According to Eq. (5-5), the ascending branch of the compressive stress-strain response is represented by the second part (segment B-C) in Fig. (5-6) (A).

$$f_c = \varepsilon_c E_c (1 - \alpha) \tag{5-5}$$

Where E_c is the concrete's elastic modulus of elasticity, ε_c is the compression strain corresponding to the specific compressive stress in concrete and α is a modifying factor connected to the compressive stress-strain response of the UHPC this value can be found using Eq. (5-6) [54].

$$\alpha = 0.001 e^{\frac{\varepsilon_c E_c}{0.243 f'c}} - 0.001 \tag{5-6}$$

At last, the branch that descends (segment C–D in Fig. (5-6) (A)) is indicated by a stress of $0.2f_c$.

In terms of UHPC's tensile stress-strain response (see Fig. (5-6) (B)), three branches represent the entire stress-strain curve. The first branch terminated at the elastic state's edge $(\varepsilon_{u1}, \sigma_{u1})$, the second at the stress maximum $(\varepsilon_{u\max}, \sigma_{u\max})$ [56], and the third denotes the descending branch $(\varepsilon_{uu}, \sigma_{uu})$. As suggested by [57], the ultimate strain value was determined to be 0.05. It should be emphasized that the damage in UHPC was also used to represent concrete crushing and cracking in tension and compression, respectively, in a manner similar to that explained for NC. The damage factor (d)

is introduced in both NC and UHPC concrete types to represent the descending portion of curves upon reaching the stress limit.

Fig. (5-6) The UHPC stress-strain relationship, (A) Compressive [54] and (B) Tensile model [49, 56], for UHPC with a steel fibre content of 2-3 vol.%.

5.1.2.3 Model of steel and GFRP bars reinforcement

The longitudinal and transverse steel reinforcement of the beam reinforcement utilized in the validation study were defined by an elastic-plastic model that was based on Von-Mises plasticity and defined by the elastic modulus (E_s), yield strength (f_y), ultimate strength (f_u), and corresponding ultimate plastic strain (ϵ_u). Although E_s and ν_s were typically measured at 210 GPa and 0.3, respectively, other values were obtained directly from the experimental reference [6], [23], as stated in Chapter three. To lessen stress concentration and local concrete failure, steel plates were added beneath the loading and support points using a model similar to this one but without the yielding feature.

For the GFRP bars reinforced the UHPC overlay, a linear elastic model denoted by the elastic modulus (E_G) and Poisson's ratio (ν_G) was employed. The tensile strength (f_{Gu}) of 827 MPa, an E_G of 46 GPa, and a ν_G of 0.33 were considered to be the typical characteristics of the GFRP bars [30]. While the GFRP bars' failure was not clearly defined, their stresses were tracked and compared with f_{Gu}

during the post-processing of the results, offering a different way to find GFRP rupture.

A schematic of the stress-strain curves used for GFRP and steel reinforcements is shown in Fig. (5-7).

Fig. (5-7) Relationship between tensile stress and strain in steel and GFRP reinforcement.

5.2 FE model validation

The presented FE model was tested for accuracy and fidelity using multiple experimental results. The load versus mid-span deflection curves for each of the ten modelled beams campaigns are plotted in Fig. (5-8) based on data from FE simulations and experiments. It is evident that the model had an outstanding match when it came to tracing the whole load-deflection response. In the majority of instances, the numerical curves' stiffness at various points (such as pre-cracking, post-yielding, and post-peak) likewise matched that of the tests, as shown in Fig. (5-8).

As shown in Table (5-3), the model was also able to predict a number of milestones within these curves, such as loads at cracking, yielding of steel reinforcement, and ultimate loads and their corresponding deflections. The ratio

of the predicted to the tested loads at the ultimate load and ultimate deflection varied from 0.90 to 1.06 and 1.0 to 1.11, respectively.

The different failure modes that were seen for the beams in experimental tests, and those that the FE simulation predicted are plotted in Fig. (5-9). The UHPC overlay's cracking was predicted by the model with reasonable level of accuracy.

The numerous findings in this section demonstrate the predictability and dependability of the FE model that is being presented, and they also provide compelling evidence for a parametric study on RC beams strengthened with GFRP-reinforced UHPC overlay.

Fig. (5-8) Experimental and numerical load versus mid-span deflection comparison (continue).

Fig. (5-8) Experimental and numerical load versus mid-span deflection comparison (continued).

Table (5-3) Key results from FE and experiment are compared.

Specimens	Ultimate load			Deflection at ultimate load		
	Exp.	FE	Exp./FE	Exp.	FE	Exp./FE
CB	32.12	32.70	0.98	37.2	35.0	1.06
B30	41.82	42.26	0.9	12.4	11.5	1.08
B50	52.73	49.96	1.05	4.1	3.7	1.11
B30G2	93.27	93.84	0.99	23.9	21.5	1.11
B50G2	106.94	110.78	0.97	28.6	26.9	1.06
B30G3L1.5	97.18	97.16	1.00	13.9	12.6	1.10
B50G3L1.5	114.83	107.83	1.06	16.7	15.2	1.10
B30E	39.21	41.11	0.95	32.7	30.8	1.06
B30G2E	117.82	112	1.05	65.9	66.1	1.0

CB

B30

B50

Fig. (5-9) Comparison experimental specimens failure modes with numerical equivalents (continue).

Fig. (5-9) Comparison experimental specimen's failure modes with numerical equivalents (continue).

Fig. (5-9) Comparison experimental specimen's failure modes with numerical equivalents (continued).

5.3 Parametric study

In the experimental program, only a small number of specimens were tested; however, more parameters can be examined to improve understanding of the performance of the GFRP-reinforced UHPC overlay strengthened beams using the validated numerical model. More bar diameter values (GFRP ratio) are presented in this section, along with a comparison between the same diameters of CFRP rebar and steel. Investigating the impact of UHPC overlay thickness, NC compression strength is also presented in this chapter as shown in Table (5-4).

Table (5-4) Parametric study details.

NO.	Parametric study	description	No. of specimens
1.	Steel reinforcement ratio	2φ10, 8 & 6mm	3
2.	GFRP reinforcement ratio	2φ8 & 6mm	2
3.	CFRP reinforcement ratio	2φ10, 8 & 6mm	3
4.	GFRP reinforcement length	2 φ10mm L=1500mm	1
5.	NC Compression strength	20 and 60 MPa	2

5.3.1 Steel reinforcement ratio

To evaluate this parameter, different ratios of steel rebar were used in UHPC overlay thickness 30mm, reinforced by 3.492%, 2.234%, and 1.257% which correspond to reinforcement of 2 φ 10mm (B30S2D10E), 2 φ 8mm (B30S2D8E) and 2 φ 6mm (B30S2D6E), respectively.

The results showed that used steel rebar in UHPC overlay strip thick-30mm with various ratio by 3.492%, 2.234%, and 1.257%, led to increase ultimate load capacity by 134%, 93% and 57%, and by 86%, 53% and 25% in comparison with control beam (CB-FE) and plain UHPC overlay strip thick-30mm (B30E-EF), respectively, as shown in Fig. (5-10).

Fig. (5-10) UHPC overlay-reinforced various steel rebar ratio; (A) load-deflection curve comparison between unstrengthened beam and plain overlay; (B) load and various steel rebar ratio.

5.3.2 GFRP reinforcement ratio

In the experimental program, 2 ϕ 10 GFRP rebar's were used to reinforce the UHPC overlay in beam B30G2E-FE, giving a reinforcement ratio of 3.49% in relation to the overlay cross-section. In this section, two additional ratios of 2.23% and 1.25%, which correspond to reinforcement of 2 ϕ 8 mm (B30G2D8E) and 2 ϕ 6mm (B30G2D6E), respectively, are used to parametric study in this section.

The ultimate load of the strengthened beams over the control ones decreased significantly when the GFRP reinforcement ratio was reduced. When compared to B30G2E-FE, the decline was nonlinear, falling by 22% and 40% of B30G2D8E and B30G2D6E, respectively. However, as illustrated in Fig. (5-11), the increase in the ultimate load capacity of B30G2D8E and B30G2D6E was 168 and 106%, and by 113% and 64% when compared to CB-FE and B30E-EF, respectively.

Fig. (5-11) (A) Comparison of the load-deflection curves of unstrengthened beam and plain overlay with UHPC overlay-reinforced various GFRP rebar ratio; (B) load and various GFRP rebar ratio.

5.3.3 CFRP reinforcement ratio

Several CFRP rebar ratios were used in UHPC overlay thickness 30mm to evaluate this parameter. These ratios were reinforced by 3.492%, 2.234%, and 1.257%, which translates to reinforcement of 2 φ 10mm (B30C2D10E), 2 φ 8mm (B30C2D8E), and 2 φ 6mm (B30C2D6E), respectively. The CFRP bars assumed to have 2172 MPa and 124 GPa ultimate strength and elastic modulus, respectively [32].

In comparison with the CB-FE and B30E-EF, respectively, the results showed that the use of CFRP rebar in UHPC overlay strip thick-30mm with various ratio by 1.257%, 2.234%, and 3.492%, and led to an increase in ultimate load capacity by 256%, 304%, and 304%, and by 183%, 221%, and 221%, Fig. (5-12). The failure in the compression zone is the reason for the inability to increase the ultimate load capacity even with an increase in the CFRP overlay's ratio of reinforcement, as shown in Fig. (5-12), that was agreed well with the previous research such as Tanarslan [5].

Fig. (5-12) (A) Examining the load-deflection curves of plain overlay and unstrengthened beams with UHPC overlay-reinforced CFRP rebar ratios; (B) comparing load and CFRP rebar ratios.

5.3.4 GFRP reinforcement length

This parameter was studied by decreasing the ratio of GFRP rebar with length of bar is equal 1500mm that placed in mid span of beam from 3 ϕ 10mm (B30G3L1.5-FE), to 2 ϕ 10mm (B30G2L1.5).

The results showed that the use of B30G2L1.5 resulted in an insignificant decrease in the ultimate load capacity by 8% and 5%, respectively, when compared to the B30G3L1.5-FE and B30G2-FE, respectively. This is a significant from a cost standpoint. Fig. (5-13) is plotted compared curves with this parametric study.

Fig. (5-13) Load-deflection curve comparison between B30G3L1.5FE, B30G2-FE and B30G2L1.5.

5.3.5 NC Compression strength

In this section, the compressive strength ($f'c$) of the concrete used in the beams for RC beams strengthened with GFRP-reinforced UHPC overlay (B30G2E-FE) is studied using two values: 20 and 60 MPa, in additional 35 MPa.

The results revealed that the use of different NC compression strengths of 20 and 60 MPa led to a decrease in ultimate load capacity of 5% and an increase of 10%

when compared with B30G2E-FE, which had a 35 MPa compression strength (see Fig. (5-14)).

Fig. (5-14) The load and different compression strengths of an RC beam are compared in (A); the load-deflection curves are compared in (B).

5.4 Summary of results of Parametric study

This section presents a comparison of all previous parametric studies conducted on the ultimate load and deflection curve, as well as an increase in the ultimate load capacity value. The ultimate load of each parametric study was listed in Table (5-5) and Fig. (5-15). Fig. (5-16) plotted the ultimate load and various reinforcement ratio for CFRP, GFRP and steel.

Fig. (5-15) shows that the beams strengthened by UHPC layer reinforced with GFRP and CFRP bars have higher initial stiffness compared to unstrengthened beams and beam strengthened by UHPC layer reinforced with steel bars. In addition, the beams with CFRP and GFRP reinforcement have higher ultimate load compared to those with steel reinforcement in the UHPC overlay. This is caused by the ability of the composite bars (CFRP and GFRP) to sustain more loads compared to steel bars. Particularly, ultimate strength of CFRP and GFRP were 2172 and 827 MPa respectively, while it was 477 MPa for steel.

Table (5-5) Results of parametric study.

CHAPTER 5 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Beam ID	Ultimate load (P_u) (kN)	% ¹ Increases to CB-FE	% ² Increases to B30E-FE	% ³ Increases to B30G2E-FE
CB-FE	32.70	-	-	-
B30E-FE	41.12	26	-	-
B30G2E-FE	112.00	243	172	-
B30G2D8E	87.60	168	113	-22 ⁴
B30G2D6E	67.50	106	64	-40
B30G2L1.5	89.05	172	117	-20
B30C2D10E	132.10	304	221	18
B30C2D8E	132.128	304	221	18
B30C2D6E	116.37	256	183	4
B30S2D10E	76.56	134	86	-32
B30S2D8E	62.97	93	53	-44
B30S2D6E	51.38	57	25	-54
B30G2EF20	106.95	227	160	-5
B30G2EF60	123.60	278	201	10

¹ % For example, the calculation for B30G2D8E (%) is as follows:
 $[P_u(BB30G2D8E) - P_u(CB FE)/P_u(CB FE)] \times 100$.

² % For example, the calculation for B30G2D8E (%) is as follows:
 $[P_u(BB30G2D8E) - P_u(B30E FE)/P_u(B30E FE)] \times 100$.

³ % For example, the calculation for B30G2D8E (%) is as follows:
 $[P_u(BB30G2D8E) - P_u(B30G2E FE)/P_u(B30G2E FE)] \times 100$.

⁴ - = decrease.

Fig. (5-15) Response to load versus deflection in beams with strengthening schemes in parametric study, (A) CFRP reinforced in UHPC overlay, (B) GFRP reinforced in UHPC overlay, (C) Steel reinforced in UHPC overlay (continue).

Fig. (5-15) Response to load versus deflection in beams with strengthening schemes in parametric study, (A) CFRP reinforced in UHPC overlay, (B) GFRP reinforced in UHPC overlay, (C) Steel reinforced in UHPC overlay (continued).

Fig. (5-16) Load vs. rebar ratio for in beams with strengthening schemes in parametric study.

5.5 Concluding remarks

1. Overall, a close agreement was observed between the numerical model and the experimental data. This encompassed various aspects such as ultimate forces, displacements and failure modes.
2. The ultimate load capacity decreased linearly from 22% to 40% as a result of the expected decrease in the GFRP reinforcement ratio, which went from 3.492% (2 ϕ 10mm) to 2.235% (2 ϕ 8) and then down to 1.257% (2 ϕ 6mm).
3. The ultimate load of a UHPC overlay is enhanced when steel reinforcement is incorporated. In particular, using of overlay's steel rebar with ratios of 3.492%, 2.235% and 1.257% increases the ultimate load by 86%, 53%, and 25% in comparison to the plain UHPC strengthened beam and by 134%, 93%, and 57% in comparison to the unstrengthened beam.
4. The utilization of CFRP rebar in the UHPC overlay, with the same ratio as mentioned in points 2 and 3, resulted in a notable enhancement of the ultimate load capacity. Specifically, the increase was observed to be 304% and 256% when compared to the unstrengthened beam, 183% and 221% when compared to a plain UHPC overlay strengthened beam, and 18% and 4% when compared to a UHPC overlay with the same area reinforced using GFRP rebar in the strengthened beam.
5. FE analysis indicates that it can be disregarded, as CFRP rebar with a ratio of 1.257% (2 ϕ 6 mm) is equivalent to GFRP rebar with an area of 3.492% (2 ϕ 10 mm) in diffracted by 4%.
6. The ultimate load was reduced by an insignificant 5% when two GFRP bars, each measuring 1500 mm, were placed in the centre of an RC beam. On the other hand, utilizing two 1500 mm long GFRP bars saved 50% of the cost when compared to those that were one piece (2210 mm).
7. Finally, increasing the normal concrete (NC) compression strength in RC beam from 20 MPa to 60 MPa resulted in 5% decrease and 10% increase in the ultimate load capacity, respectively

CHAPTER 6 : ANALYTICAL MODEL

6.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to predict the ultimate load capacity for specimens tested in an experimental work and a parametric study in FE method. Developing such model to predict the ultimate load of the strengthened beams can save time for engineers and professionals to use this technique with a need for further research. In addition, validating this model against this wide range of specimens with various investigated parameters can increase the reliability of this model.

6.2 Design guideline proposal

The development of practical guidelines for the design of RC beams strengthened by UHPC overlays with GFRP-reinforced is one of the study's objectives. By taking into account the unique failure modes seen in the latter and using the actual tensile stresses in GFRP rebar at failure that were obtained from regression analysis on data from the current parametric study. The previous recommendations on UHPC overlays with or without steel and CFRP reinforcement [58,59] are extended to those with GFRP reinforcement in this work. The design steps are outlined in the subsection that follows.

6.2.1 RC beam

The guidelines in ACI 318 [33] can be used to design RC beams composed of NC. By ignoring the concrete's tensile stress and applying a uniform stress block for concrete in compression, as demonstrated in Fig. (6-1), the moment capacity (M_n) of rectangular members can be made simpler. This yields the following equation:

$$M_n = A_s f_y \left(d - \frac{a}{2} \right) \quad (6-1)$$

where the variables are the depth of the compressive stress block (a), the effective depth (d), the yield strength (f_y) of the longitudinal tensile reinforcement, and the area (A_s).

Fig. (6-1) Stress and strain diagram of RC beam.

6.2.2 RC beams with a UHPC overlay reinforced with GFRP

As illustrated in Fig. (6-2), the M_n of the RC beams strengthened with GFRP (or steel)-reinforced UHPC overlay can be computed using Eqs. (6-2) and (6-3), which is derived from the concepts of force equilibrium and strain compatibility [59]:

Fig. (6-2) Stress and strain diagram of RC beam strengthened with reinforced UHPC overlay.

$$Mn = A_s f_y \left(d_1 - \frac{a}{2} \right) + A_{ru} f_{ru} \left(d_2 - \frac{a}{2} \right) + A_u f_{tu} \left(d_u - \frac{a}{2} \right) + A'_s f'_y \left(\frac{a}{2} - d' \right) \quad (6-2)$$

and

$$a = \frac{A_s f_y + A_{ru} f_{ru} + A_u f_{tu} - A'_s f'_y}{0.85 f'_c b_w} \quad (6-3)$$

where:

f_y : Stress experienced by the longitudinal tensile reinforcement.

d_1 : The distance from the top face of the beam to the center of the tensile reinforcement.

A_{ru} : The area covered by overlay reinforcement.

f_{ru} : Stress in the overlay reinforcement.

d_2 : The distance from the top face of the beam to the center of the overlay reinforcement.

A_u : The cross-sectional area, calculated as the product of the beam's width (b_w) and thickness (h_u), of the overlay.

f_{tu} : The tensile strength of Ultra-High-Performance Concrete (UHPC).

d_u : The distance from the top face of the beam to the center of the overlay.

h and b_w : Representing the beam's height and width, respectively.

A'_s : Denoting the area occupied by longitudinal compressive reinforcement in the RC beam.

f'_y : Stress experienced by the longitudinal compressive reinforcement in the RC beam.

d' : The distance from the top face of the beam to the centre of its compressive reinforcement.

With Mn established, it is simple to calculate the ultimate load (P_u) by considering the particular loading configuration and boundary conditions. The approach described in this section can be used to estimate the load-bearing capacity of beams reinforced with a UHPC overlay, regardless of whether they are unreinforced or reinforced with steel rebar, GFRP, or CFRP. This is an important point to make. It is easy to modify Eq. (6-2) by leaving out the second term in the former case or by adding the appropriate strength (failure stress for FRP or yielding strength for steel) in the latter.

The analysis includes a number of scenarios concerning the longitudinal reinforcement of the beam, including (a) yielding in only the tensile steel bars and (b) yielding in both.

6.3 Previous studies

Kadhim et al. [4], carefully examined the loads and moments related to beams, paying particular attention to those reinforced with UHPC. The study used steel and CFRP to investigate both reinforced and unreinforced UHPC layer. A key tool in this analysis was Eq. (6-2), which demonstrated how well it could compare results with the FE outcomes that Kadhim et al. [4] had personally studied. Interestingly, the equation proved to be reliable when applied to UHPC overlays, regardless of whether steel reinforcement was used or not, as shown by the results shown in Fig. (6-3) (A). It was found that the Eq. (6-2) provided reasonable agreement with the beams strengthened with plain UHPC or that reinforced with steel bars. However, for those used CFRP bars as reinforcement for UHPC layer, a formalized formula (Eq. (6-4)) was developed to determine the stress that CFRP experience. Then, using Eqs. (6-2) and (6-3) in combined with Eq. (6-4) produced acceptable outcomes, which are shown graphically in Fig. (6-3) (B).

$$f_{ru} = 818f_c^{0.2}(\rho_{r\ UHPC} \times h_u)^{-0.35} \quad (6-4)$$

Fig. (6-3) Estimated load against comparing FE results using CFRP rebar's (A) tensile strength and (B) improved tensile strength (Eq. (6-4)) [4].

6.4 Predicted of experimental results

Given the information previously provided, the loads are carefully calculated using Eqs. (6-1), (6-2) and (6-3) that are especially designed for the specimens that are being examined in this study, (Fig. (6-4)).

Fig. (6-4) Shear force and bending moment diagram for the tested beams.

A thorough comparison of the results obtained from experimental testing is based on these load calculations. These findings, which are aptly illustrated in Table (6-1), are thoroughly examined in the fourth chapter of this thesis. Interestingly, the results show that the reinforced beams that is, the UHPC specimens reinforced

CHAPTER 6..... ANALYTICAL MODEL

with GFRP—perform less well than ideal for regarding Beams reinforced by UHPC with GFRP bars that are positioned and cast in place devoid of epoxy as shown in Fig. (6-5), but beams strengthened with UHPC overlay as the strips (laminates) was compared to the practical close to test results, it performed very well. This is because, as mentioned in Chapter Four of this thesis, the failure of the bond between the overlay and the beam causes the loading to continue, increasing the stress on the glass fibres and ultimately leading to the failure of the compression zone.

Table (6-1) Compared predicted with experimental results by using Eqs. (6-2) and (6-3).

Specimens ID	$P_u (Exp.)(kN)$	$P_u (pre.)(kN)$	$P_u (Exp.)/P_u (pre.)$
CB	32.12	28.71	1.12
B30	41.82	41.95	1.00
B50	52.73	54.02	0.98
B30G2	93.27	117.43	0.79
B50G2	106.94	131.45	0.81
B30G3L1.5	97.18	151.95	0.64
		138.42*	0.70
B50G3L1.5	114.83	166.96	0.69
		178.25*	0.64
B30E	39.21	41.95	0.93
B30E&A	44.64	41.95	1.06
B30G2E	117.82	117.43	1.00
B30G2E&A	73.04	78.13	0.93
standard deviation (SD)			0.15
Mean $\frac{P_u (Exp.)}{P_u (pre.)}$			0.90

* P_u @ end length of GFRP bar.

Fig. (6-5) Predicted load using the GFRP rebar's tensile strength and the matching Exp. results, as shown in Eqs. (6-2) and (6-3).

A sufficient number of specimens are required to conduct a thorough investigation with the goal of modifying Eq. (6-4) to comply with the particular requirements for modifying the GFRP stress values in beams strengthened with direct-cast UHPC. In order to ensure the derivation of an accurate and refined equation that effectively addresses the correction requirements, it is imperative that all pertinent variables be thoroughly investigated and taken into account.

Notable results were obtained when the finite element method via the ABAQUS program was utilized to examine the stresses that GFRP undergo when they fail in beams reinforced with direct-cast UHPC. According to the study, the maximum tensile stress value of 827 MPa is roughly 65-75% of the tensile stress of GFRP at the bond failure point, (see Eq. (6-5). Furthermore, failure occurs at the end of the bars length in beams where the GFRP bars stop shorter of the beam's length, leading to a shorter failure time than in the previous case. In this

CHAPTER 6..... ANALYTICAL MODEL

case, the GFRP tensile stress is between 45 and 55 percent of the maximum stress value, (see Eq. (6-6). Table (6-2) and Fig. (6-6) show how the study's application of Eq. (6-3) and modification of the GFRP ultimate stress values allows for outcome prediction. Modified

$$f_{u(GFRP)modified} = 0.7 \times f_{u(GFRP)} \quad (6-5)$$

$$f_{u(GFRP)modified} = 0.5 \times f_{u(GFRP)} \quad (6-6)$$

Table (6-2) Compared predicted with experimental results after modified GFRP stress.

Specimens ID	$P_u (Exp.)(kN)$	$P_u (pre.)(kN)$	$P_u (Exp.)/P_u (pre.)$
CB	32.12	28.71	1.12
B30	41.82	41.95	1.00
B50	52.73	54.02	0.98
B30G2	93.27	95.68	0.97
B50G2	106.94	109.12	0.98
B30G3L1.5	97.18	99.36	0.98
B50G3L1.5	114.83	112.90	1.02
B30E	39.21	41.95	0.93
B30E&A	44.64	41.95	1.06
B30G2E	117.82	117.43	1.00
B30G2E&A	73.04	78.13	0.93
Standard Deviation (SD)			0.05
Mean $\frac{P_u (Exp.)}{P_u (pre.)}$			1.00

Fig. (6-6) Predicted load using modified of the GFRP rebar's tensile stress.

Table (6-2) presents the model predictions $P_u(pre)$ and P_u from the tests ($P_u(exp.)$) for the experimental specimens examined in this investigation. Because the ultimate tensile stress of GFRP rebar was modified and used in Eqs. (6-5) and (6-6) there is a good match between experimental results and model predictions, as evidenced by the mean of ($P_u(exp.)/P_u(pre)$) of 1.00 with a standard deviation of 0.05.

6.5 Predicted of FE results

Table (6-3) and Fig. (6-7) show the comparison the results outcome FE method that conducted in chapter fifth of this thesis with predicted results by Eq. (6-3) and used modified stress of GFRP, Eq. (6-4) for CFRP and directed the use yield stress of steel reinforcement.

CHAPTER 6..... ANALYTICAL MODEL

Table (6-3) Compared predicted with FE results after modified FRP stress.

Specimens ID	$P_u (FE)(kN)$	$P_u (pre.)(kN)$	$P_u (FE)/P_u (pre.)$
CB-FE	32.7	28.71	1.14
B30E-FE	41.11	41.95	0.98
B30G2E-FE	112	117.43	0.95
B30G2D8E	87.6	90.92	0.96
B30G2D6E	67.5	69.94	0.97
B30G2L1.5	89.05	94.59	0.94
B30C2D10E	132.1	181.64	0.73*
B30C2D8E	132.128	147.56	0.90
B30C2D6E	116.37	118.33	0.98
B30S2D10E	76.56	76.61	1.00
B30S2D8E	62.97	64.33	0.98
B30S2D6E	51.38	54.61	0.94
B30G2EF20	106.95	110.05	0.97
B30G2EF60	123.6	120.62	1.02
Standard Deviation (SD)			0.03
Mean $\frac{P_u (Exp.)}{P_u (pre.)}$			0.97

* Compression failure occurs in first state from loading.

The model predictions ($P_u(pre)$) and test results ($P_u(FE)$) for the FE specimens and parametric study are shown in Fig. (6–7). The GFRP rebar's ultimate tensile stress was modified in Eqs. (6-5) and (6-6), which is why there is an excellent correlation between the model predictions and FE results. A mean value of ($P_u(FE)/P_u(pre)$) of 0.97 with a standard deviation of 0.03 lends support to this.

Fig. (6-7) Compared the anticipated and FE findings following the modified FRP stress.

6.6 Conclusion observations

1. Using GFRP stress reduction has shown to be very effective, especially in situations where bond failure is predicted. The reduction that has been attained represents a noteworthy 65-75% of the failure tensile stress that the fibres encountered.
2. The reduction in GFRP stress is marginally lower than the first point when GFRP bars are used in the bending zone, provided their length is less than the beam's. This decrease represents 45–55% of the value of the failure tensile stress. Interestingly, failure happens in UHPC near the end of the bars length and happens faster than it did in the first instance.
3. Eq. (6-4) is a predictive tool that can be used to estimate the tensile stress in CFRP-reinforced of UHPC overlays. It is derived from previous studies.
4. Eqs. (6-5) & (6-6) incorporate the tensile stress of the GFRP reinforcement inside the UHPC overlay directly, producing extremely pleasing outcomes. An effective method for projecting and evaluating the performance of the reinforced system is offered by this direct application.

CHAPTER 7 : CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

7.1 Introduction

Investigating the influence performance of plain UHPC overlay and that reinforced with GFRP bars in strengthening RC beams was the main focus of this thesis. A comprehensive program of experiments was carried out to accomplish this aim. The tests conducted as part of this experimental program is including unstrengthened beams and GFRP-reinforced UHPC overlay. ABAQUS/Standard was also used in the study to obtain additional understanding of the structural behaviour of the elements under investigation. In general, the study showed that RC beams' impact behaviour can be enhanced by using the UHPC overlay plain and reinforced with GFRP strengthening method. For this reason, it is advised to use this technique to strengthen RC beams.

7.2 Research conclusions

The research tasks completed lead to the following conclusions:

7.2.1 Experimental program

1. In general, it has been discovered that the behaviour of RC members can be significantly enhanced by using the UHPC overlay when strengthening them. These improvements are dependent on a number of factors, including the bond interface between surfaces, the use of laminates or cast-in situ of UHPC overlay, presence of reinforcement in UHPC overlay, etc.
2. The ultimate load of the plain UHPC overlay strengthened beams was increased by 30% to 64% when compared to the control beam. These beams are primarily prone to flexure failure following UHPC layer rupture.
3. Compared to the control, the GFRP-reinforced UHPC overlay achieved an ultimate load of 190%–267%. This kind of failure occurred in the crushing compression NC zone after debonding.
4. Increasing the thickness of the UHPC layer from 30 to 50 mm led to a 26% increase in the ultimate load for plain overlay specimens and a 15% increase

CHAPTER 7..... CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

for reinforced overlay specimens. In comparison to the control beam, this also made the plain overlay stiffer; however, the reinforced overlay's stiffness and ductility both increased.

5. The affected amount of use three bars measuring 1500 mm and two measuring the entire length of the beam were given increase in ultimate load by 4% and 7% of the equivalent thickness, respectively.
6. There is about a 14% reduction in the strain on steel when comparing plain overlay to reinforced overlay.
7. It was found through studying the load-deflection curves of the beams reinforced by UHPC overlay with reinforced GFRP bars during the experimental work that when UHPC cracks, there is no yielding in the curves.

7.2.2 Numerical modelling

1. A close agreement was found between the numerical model and the experimental data, which included the ultimate forces, displacements, failure modes, strain development.
2. The ultimate load capacity decreased from 22% to 40% as a result of the predicted response of decreasing the area of GFRP reinforcement from 3.492% ($2\phi 10\text{mm}$) to 2.235% ($2\phi 8$) and then down to 1.257% ($2\phi 6\text{mm}$), with a linear behaviour of decrease.
3. When steel reinforcement is used in UHPC overlay, the overlay's behaviour is improved in the ultimate load. Specifically, when compared to a control beam, the overlay's steel rebar area increases by 134, 93, and 57%, respectively, and when compared to a plain UHPC strengthened beam, it increases by 86, 53, and 25% of the same steel area.
4. Application of CFRP rebar in UHPC overlay with same area in points 2 and 3 indicated an increase in ultimate load capacity of 304% and 256% compared to unstrengthened beam, 183% and 221% compared to plain

CHAPTER 7..... CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

UHPC overlay strengthened beam, and 18% and 4% compared to UHPC overlay with reinforced same area of GFRP rebar in strengthened beam.

5. CFRP rebar with an area of 56.57 mm^2 ($2\phi 6 \text{ mm}$) is equivalent to GFRP rebar with an area of 157.14 mm^2 ($2\phi 10 \text{ mm}$) in diffracted by 4%, showing that it can be ignored, as determined by FE analysis.
6. Using two GFRP bars, each length 1500 mm and positioned in the middle of an RC beam, resulted in a negligible 5% reduction in the ultimate load, when compared to using three bars of GFRP of the same length and location. In contrast, using two GFRP bars, each measuring 1500 mm, resulted in a 50% cost reduction compared to those with entire length (2210 mm).

7.2.3 Analytical conclusion

1. Stress reduction through GFRP has been extraordinarily effective, especially when bond failure is expected. The reduction that has been attained is a noteworthy 65-75% of the failure tensile stress that the fibres experienced. This substantial reduction in stress is essential for improving the overall durability and performance of structures and provides a noteworthy remedy in bond failure-prone situations.
2. When GFRP bars are deployed with lengths shorter than the beam's span, the GFRP stress reduction factor in the flexural zone is marginally less than it was in the first point. This reduction shows up as 45–55% of the value of the failure tensile stress. Interestingly, UHPC failure events are noticed close to the bar end and happen more quickly than they did in the first place. Gaining an understanding of these subtleties in stress reduction depending on bar length in various zones is essential for maximizing the application of GFRP in structural design and construction.

7.3 Recommendations

The behaviour of GFRP rebar in UHPC overlay strengthened RC beams subjected to flexural load is the subject of one of the first experimental studies, so it was not possible to cover every facet of this topic. Future studies in a variety of fields include may be investigated:

1. The effectiveness of UHPC overlaying a plain or reinforced strengthened RC beam under static load was investigated in this study. Still, the impact of additional *repeated load* could be investigated to see if it has any bearing on the basic UHPC or reinforced efficacy.
2. Studying the effect *fire and elevated temperature* on structural behaviour of an RC beam strengthened with plain UHPC overlay and reinforced with steel, GFRP, and CFRP, under same protocol loading in this study.
3. Response of beams strengthened with UHPC overlay (reinforced or unreinforced) under impact load could be an important topic to be investigated in further research studies.
4. Investigating an RC beam strengthened with UHPC overlay and reinforced with steel, GFRP, and CFRP in terms of its *torsional testing* behaviour.

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APPENDIX A – DESIGN OF BEAM

APPENDIX A – DESIGN OF BEAM

A-1 Design of beam

Properties of cross section

$$h = 250\text{mm}, b = 150\text{mm},$$

$$d = 250 - 20 - 8 - 4 = 218\text{mm}$$

$$A_s = 3 * \frac{\pi}{4} * 8^2 = 150\text{mm}^2, \rho = \frac{150}{150 * 218} = 0.00459$$

$$f'_c = 35\text{MPa}, f_y = 345\text{MPa}$$

$$\text{CHECK } \rho_{\min.} = \frac{1.4}{f_y} = \frac{1.4}{345} = 0.00406 < \rho \therefore \text{ok.}$$

Flexural resistance

$$M_n = A_s * f_y \left(d - \frac{a}{2} \right),$$

$$a = \frac{A_s * f_y}{0.85 * f'_c * b} = 11.6 \text{ mm},$$

$$M_n = 150 * 345 * \left(218 - \frac{11.6}{2} \right) * 10^{-6} = 10.98 \text{ kN} \cdot \text{m}$$

$$P = \frac{10.98}{0.825} * 2 = 26.62 \text{ kN}$$

APPENDIX A – DESIGN OF BEAM

Shear resistance

$$V = V_c + V_s,$$

$$V_c = 0.17 * \sqrt{f'_c} * b * d$$

$$V_c = 0.17 * \sqrt{35} * 150 * 218 * 10^{-6} = 32.9kN$$

$$V_s = \frac{2A_s * f_y * d}{S} = \frac{2 * 50 * 345 * 218}{110} * 10^{-3} = 68.4kN$$

$$\therefore V = 32.9 + 68.4 = 101.3kN$$

See the diagram

*P for shear = 2 * 101.3 = 202.6kN >> 26.62kN ∴ OK.*

APPENDIX B – SUMMARY OF MATERIAL

APPENDIX B – SUMMARY OF MATERIAL

B-1 Cement properties

Table (B-1) Chemical analysis of the cement.

Compound Composition	Ordinary Portland cement type I		Sulphate resisting Portland cement type V	
	% Weight	Iraqi Specification No. 5/1984	% Weight	Iraqi Specification No. 5/1984
Silica Dioxide (SiO ₂)	19.03	-	19.67	
Alumina Oxide (AL ₂ O ₃)	5.80		4.22	
Iron Oxide (Fe ₂ O ₃)	4.38	-	5.298	
Lime Oxide (CaO)	61.01	-	62.81	
Magnesia Oxide (MgO)	2.87	≤ 5.0%	3.412	≤ 5.0%
Chloride (CL)			0.08	≤ 0.1%
Free Lime (CaO)	1.41	-		
Sulfate Trioxide (SO ₃)	2.20	≤ 2.5% if C3A ≤ 5% ≤ 2.8% if C3A >5%	2.331	≤ 2.5% if C3A ≤ 5% ≤ 2.8% if C3A >5%
Loss on ignition (L.O.I)	2.41	≤ 4.0%	2.295	≤ 4.0%
Insoluble Residue (I.R)	0.73	≤ 1.5%	0.878	≤ 1.5%
Lime Saturation Factor (L.S.F)	0.84	0.66-1.02		
Main Compounds (Bogue's Equation) Percentage by Weight of Cement				
Tricalcium Aluminates (C ₃ A)	5.45	-	2.229	≤ 3.5%
Tricalcium Silicate (C ₃ S)	40.53	-	68.497	
Dicalcium Silicate (C ₂ S)	28.10	-	2.884	
Tricalcium Alumina Ferrite (C ₄ AF)	18.21	-	16.121	

Table (B-2) Physical properties of the cement.

Physical Characteristics	Ordinary Portland cement type I		Sulphate resisting Portland cement type V			
	Results	Limits of IQS No.5/1984	Results	Limits of IQS No.5/1984		
Specific Gravity	3.13	-	3.20			
Fineness by Blaine (m ² / kg)	340	≥230	390	≥ 300		
Setting time (Vicat) (min)	Initial Time	175	≥ 45	Initial Time	160	≥ 45
	Final Time	200	≤ 600	Final Time	239	≤ 600
Compressive strength of cement paste 50 mm cube mold (MPa)	3 days	21.20	≥ 15	7 days	28	≥ 23
	7 days	28.50	≥ 23	28 days	48	≥ 42.5

APPENDIX B – SUMMARY OF MATERIAL

B-2 Fine Aggregates properties

Table (B-3) Sieve analysis of fine aggregates

Sieve size	Passing (%)	IOS No.45/1984 (Zone2)
9.50 mm	100	100
4.75 mm (No.4)	91	90-100
2.36 mm (No.8)	83	75-100
1.18 mm (No.16)	69	55-90
0.6 mm (No.30)	56	35-59
0.3 mm (No.50)	19	8-30
0.15 mm (No.100)	7.0	0-10

Table (B-4) Physical and Chemical Properties of the Fine Aggregates

Physical Characteristics	Value	IOS No.45/1984
Specific gravity	2.60	-
Absorption	3.45%	-
Sulfate content	0.40 %	≤ 0.50 %
Material finer	0.83	≤ 1.0 %

B-3 Coarse aggregates properties

Table (B-5) Sieve Analysis of Coarse Aggregates

Sieve size (mm)	% Passing	IQS No. 45/1984 Limits (5-14) mm
20	100	100
14	93	90-100
10	72	50-85
5	6	0-10
2.36	2.5	-

Table (B-6) Physical Properties and Sulfate Content of Coarse Aggregates

Physical Properties	Values	IQS No. 45/1984 Limits
Specific gravity	2.65	-
Sulfate content	0.05%	≤ 0.1 %
Absorption	0.78%	-
percentage loss in Loss Anglos test	18.5%	≤ 35%
Clay	0.14%	0.2%

APPENDIX B – SUMMARY OF MATERIAL

B-4 GFRP properties

الخصائص وقيم الأداء

1. القوة الميكانيكية والاستقرار

قيم الأداء	خصائص المنتج
الحد الأدنى: 800 MPa	قوة الشد
الحد الأدنى 50,000 ميجا باسكال	(معامل يونغ) معامل المرونة
الحد الأدنى: 12 ميجا باسكال	التصاق الشد بالخرسانة
الحد الأدنى 600 ميجا باسكال	المقاومة في البيئة القلوية
الحد الأدنى 10 ميجا باسكال	التصاق شد بالخرسانة بعد البيئة القلوية
الحد الأدنى 200 ميجا باسكال	قوة الشد المستعرض
2,2x 10 ⁻³ (1/°C)	التمدد الحراري

2. الخصائص الهندسية

تم قياس القطر الاسمي والمقطع العرضي الاسمي بما يتماشى مع المادة 5 من ISO 10406.

Nominal diameter, Ø	4,0	6,0	8,0	10	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26
Cross sectional area, mm ²	10	30	50	80	100	140	200	260	300	350	400	450

3. التصاق الشد بالخرسانة

تم تحديدها وفقاً للمادة 7 من ISO 10406-1.

Nominal diameter, Ø	4,0	6,0	8,0	10	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26
Adhesion Tension with concrete	19,7	23,4	12,1	16,1	13,0	12,1	12,2	12,8	12,3	12,1	12,2	12,6

4. مقاومة الشد

نتائج التجارب التي تم إجراؤها وفقاً للمادة 6 من ISO 10406-1 هي كما يلي:

Nominal diameter, Ø	4,0	6,0	8,0	10	12	14	16	18	20	22	24	26
Tensile strength, Mpa	1068	828	997	895	1101	1169	1063	911	1053	872	895	1096

APPENDIX B – SUMMARY OF MATERIAL

B-5 Epoxy properties

In below product data sheet for Sikadur 32 epoxy used in this study.

PRODUCT DATA SHEET

Sikadur®-32 LP

Epoxy structural bonding agent for use at high temperatures

DESCRIPTION

Sikadur®-32 LP is a 2-part, epoxy based structural bonding agent for use at high temperatures. It is moisture tolerant and can bond wet or dry materials to damp or dry substrates.

USES

Sikadur®-32 LP may only be used by experienced professionals.

As a structural bonding agent and adhesive for:

- Concrete elements (including bonding fresh to hardened concrete)
- Hard natural stone
- Ceramics, fibre-cement
- Mortar, Bricks, Masonry, Render
- Steel, Iron, Aluminium
- Wood
- Polyester / fibreglass and epoxy resin materials
- Glass

CHARACTERISTICS / ADVANTAGES

- Application temperature range +20 °C to +40 °C
- Thickness up to 1 mm
- Easy to mix and apply
- Suitable for dry and damp concrete substrates
- Very good adhesion to many construction materials
- Hardens without shrinkage
- Different coloured parts (for mixing control)
- No primer needed
- High initial and ultimate mechanical strengths
- Impermeable to liquids and water vapour

SUSTAINABILITY

- Conformity with LEED v4 MRc 4 (Option 2): Building Product Disclosure and Optimization - Material Ingredients
- Conformity with LEED v2009 IEQc 4.1: Low-Emitting Materials - Adhesives and Sealants

APPROVALS / CERTIFICATES

- CE Marking and Declaration of Performance to EN 1504-4 - Structural bonding

PRODUCT INFORMATION

Composition	Epoxy resin and selected fillers	
Packaging	Parts A+B	5 kg ready to mix unit Pallets of 390 units (450 kg)
	Parts A+B	1,2 kg ready to mix unit Box of 6 units (7,2 kg)
	Refer to current price list for packaging variations	
Colour	Part A	white
	Part B	dark grey
	Parts A+B mixed	concrete grey
Shelf life	24 months from date of production	

PRODUCT DATA SHEET
Sikadur®-32 LP
December 2020, Version 02.01
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APPENDIX B – SUMMARY OF MATERIAL

Mixing ratio	Part A : Part B = 2 : 1 by weight or volume		
Consumption	~1,3 kg/m ² per mm of thickness. This figure is theoretical and does not allow for any additional material due to surface porosity, surface profile, variations in level or wastage etc.		
Layer thickness	~1 mm max.		
Sag flow	Non-sag up to 1,0 mm thickness on vertical surfaces		(EN 1799)
Product temperature	+20 °C min. / +40 °C max.		
Ambient air temperature	+20 °C min. / +40 °C max.		
Dew point	Beware of condensation. Steel substrate temperature during application must be at least +3 °C above dew point.		
Substrate temperature	+20 °C min. / +40 °C max.		
Substrate moisture content	Cementitious substrates must be dry or matt damp (no standing water). Brush the adhesive well into the substrate if matt damp.		
Pot Life	Temperature	Potlife*	Open time (EN ISO 9514)
	+20 °C	~145 minutes	~270 minutes
	+30 °C	~55 minutes	~240 minutes
	+40 °C	~35 minutes	~120 minutes
*200 g The potlife begins when Parts A+B are mixed. It is shorter at high temperatures and longer at low temperatures. The greater the quantity mixed, the shorter the potlife. To obtain longer workability at high temperatures, the mixed adhesive may be divided into smaller quantities. Another method is to chill Parts A+B before mixing (not below +5 °C).			

BASIS OF PRODUCT DATA

All technical data stated in this Product Data Sheet are based on laboratory tests. Actual measured data may vary due to circumstances beyond our control.

IMPORTANT CONSIDERATIONS

- Sikadur® resins are formulated to have low creep under permanent loading. However due to the creep behaviour of all polymer materials under load, when using adhesive for structural applications, the long term structural design load must account for creep. Generally the long term structural design load must be lower than 20–25 % of the failure load. A structural engineer must be consulted for design calculations for specific structural applications.
- When using multiple units during application, do not mix the following unit until the previous one has been used in order to avoid a reduction in workability and handling time.
- For heavy components positioned vertically or overhead, provide temporary support.

ECOLOGY, HEALTH AND SAFETY

For information and advice on the safe handling, storage and disposal of chemical products, users shall refer to the most recent Safety Data Sheet (SDS) containing physical, ecological, toxicological and other safety-related data.

APPLICATION INSTRUCTIONS

SUBSTRATE QUALITY

Concrete / masonry / mortar / stone

Concrete and mortar must be at least 3–6 weeks old. Substrate surfaces must be sound, clean, dry or matt damp. Free from standing water, ice, dirt, oil, grease, coatings, laitance, efflorescence, old surface treatments, all loose particles and any other surface contaminants that could affect adhesion of the bonding agent.

Steel

Surfaces must be clean, dry, free from oil, grease, coatings, rust, scale, all loose particles and any other surface contaminants that could affect adhesion of the bonding agent.

Wood

Substrate surfaces must be sound, clean, dry and free from dirt, oil, grease, coatings, all loose particles and any other surface contaminants that could affect adhesion of the bonding agent.

Polyester / epoxy / ceramics / glass

Surfaces must be clean, dry, free from oil, grease and any other surface contaminants that could affect adhesion of the bonding agent.

SUBSTRATE PREPARATION

Concrete / masonry / mortar / stone

Substrates must be prepared mechanically using suitable abrasive blast cleaning, needle gunning, light scabbling, bush hammering, grinding or other suitable equipment to achieve an open textured gripping surface profile.

APPENDIX C – EXPERIMENTAL UHPC MIX

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Table (C-1) Trial UHPC Mix.

No.	Cement type	Cement kg/m ³	Sand kg/m ³	Silica fume kg/m ³	Steel type	Steel fibre kg/m ³	Superplasticizer %	Water %	Compressive Strength at 7 days of age.	Compressive Strength at 28 days of age.
1	(O.P.C.) KARASTA	950	1050	190	1*	118 (1.5%)	2.5	20	51	--
2	(O.P.C.) KARASTA	950	1050	190	1*	118 (1.5%)	2.5	18	58	--
3	(O.P.C.) KARASTA	950	1050	190	1*	142 (1.8%)	2.5	18	65	--
4	(O.P.C.) KARASTA	950	1050	190	1*	157 (2%)	2.5	18	69	--
5	(O.P.C.) KARASTA	950	1050	190	1*	157 (2%)	3.0	16	74	--
6	(O.P.C.) KARASTA	950	1050	190	2*	157 (2%)	3.0	16	85	97
7	(O.P.C.) KARASTA	950	1050	190	2*	157 (2%)	3.2	16	83	98
8	(O.P.C.) KARASTA	950	1050	190	2*	157 (2%)	3.5	15	85	95
9	(O.P.C.) MASS	950	1050	190	2*	157 (2%)	3.5	16	88	100

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No.	Cement type	Cement kg/m ³	Sand kg/m ³	Silica fume kg/m ³	Steel type	Steel fibre kg/m ³	Superplasticizer %	Water %	Compressive Strength at 7 days of age.	Compressive Strength at 28 days of age.
10	(O.P.C.) MASS	950	1050	190	2*	157 (2%)	3.5	16	90	106
11	(O.P.C.) MASS	950	1050	190	3*	157 (2%)	3.5	15	93	115
12	(O.P.C.) MASS	940	1050	200	3*	157 (2%)	3.5	15	94	118
13	(S.R.C.) AL JESR	950	1050	190	3*	157 (2%)	3.5	15	103	119
14	(S.R.C.) AL JESR	950	1050	190	3*	157 (2%)	3.5	15	112	128
15	(S.R.C.) AL JESR	950	1050	190	3*	157 (2%)	3.5	15	110	130

* Use multiple companies that produce steel fibre.

APPENDIX D – TEST OF HARDEN CONCRETE-STATE PROPERTIES

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D-1 Cubical compression test

The cubical compressive strength (f_{cu}) for each batch was determined after 28 days, calculated as the average of the compressive strength from three concrete cubes (Eq. D-1). Additionally, the fracture type of each specimen, whether NC or UHPC, was documented at the conclusion of each test, as shown in Table (D-1) and Table (D-2).

$$f_{cu} = \frac{P}{A} \quad \dots\dots\dots \quad (D-1)$$

where:

P = peak load (N).

A = specimen cross-sectional area (mm²).

f_{cu} = cubical compressive strength (MPa).

Table (D-1) Results of cube compressive strength test NC.

Specimen	Density kg/m ³	compressive strength (28 days) MPa
1	2395	41.13
2	2408	44.27
3	2412	45.86
4	2554	50.61
5	2537	47.45
6	2437	43.87
Average	2457	45.53

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Table (D-3) Results of test of splitting tensile strength NC.

Specimen	P (kN)	(MPa)
1	148.3	4.7
2	129.7	4.1
3	114.1	3.6
Average	130.7	4.2

Table (D-4) Results of test of splitting tensile strength UHPC.

Specimen	P (kN)	(MPa)
1	476.0	15.1
2	463.6	14.8
3	451.6	14.4
Average	463.7	14.8

D-3 Flexural tensile test (Modulus of Rupture)

The flexural strength of each specimen was determined using the following equations (adopted from ASTM C78 / C78M – 18 standard test. Table (D-5) and Table (D-6).

- The fracture takes place outside the middle third by less than 5% of the span length:

$$f_r = \frac{3Pa}{bd^2} \dots\dots\dots (D-3)$$

where:

f_r = modulus of rupture (MPa),

P = peak load (N),

L = span length c/c (mm),

b = average width (mm),

d = average depth (mm) and

APPENDIX D – TEST OF HARDEN CONCRETE-STATE PROPERTIES

a = average distance between the line of the fracture and the nearest support

Table (D-5) Results of flexural tensile test (modulus of rupture) NC.

Specimen	P (kN)	(MPa)
1	15.17	4.55
2	14.07	4.22
3	12.33	3.7
Average	13.86	4.15

Table (D-6) Results of flexural tensile test (modulus of rupture) UHPC.

Specimen	P (kN)	(MPa)
1	18.09	21.70
2	15.89	19.06
3	14.32	17.18
Average	16.10	19.32

الخلاصة

لقد نمت الخرسانة فائقة الأداء (UHPC) أكثر فأكثر في البناء بسبب خواصها الميكانيكية الفائقة وعمرها الأطول. يعد استخدام مادة UHPC طريقة مبتكرة لتحديث أسطح الجسور والعناصر الهيكلية الأخرى، ولكن هناك عيوب أيضاً، مثل السُمك الزائد والتشقق الموضعي التي تزيد من وزن الهيكل وتكلفته. لتحسين ومعالجة هذه المشكلات، تقترح هذه الدراسة إضافة قضبان البوليمر المسلحة بالألياف الزجاجية (GFRP) إلى مادة UHPC. أجريت فحوصات تجريبية في هذا البحث لتقييم أداء العتبات الخرسانية المسلحة المقواة في الانحناء باستخدام طبقات UHPC المسلحة بقضبان GFRP.

تم استخدام اثنتي عشرة عتبةً في هذه الدراسة؛ كانت اثنتان منها عبارة عن عتبات مرجعية (غير مقواة)، وتم تقوية العينات العشرة الأخرى باستخدام مادة UHPC. كانت المتغيرات التي تم فحصها هي سمك طبقة UHPC، ووجود قضبان GFRP، وعدد وطول قضبان GFRP، وحالة السطح (مجموعتان من طرق الربط: الأولى كانت صب مادة (UHPC) بشكل مباشر على العينة، والثانية شملت كلا من الإيبوكسي فقط، والإيبوكسي + المثبتات الميكانيكية).

تم دراسة الحمل النهائي (Pu) وأنماط فشل العتبات فيما يتعلق بالطبقات البسيطة والطبقات المسلحة بقضبان GFRP. كان التشقق الموضعي في UHPC هو وضع الفشل الرئيسي، كما أدى استخدام الطبقات البسيطة إلى زيادة Pu بنسبة 30% إلى 64% و 22% إلى 39% في المجموعتين الأولى والثانية، على التوالي. أظهر هيكل العتبة الخرسانية فشلاً في الانثناء في العتبات المسلحة بطبقات GFRP، مما أدى إلى زيادة كبيرة في Pu (190%-258% و 267%) في المجموعتين الأولى والثانية، على التوالي) بالمقارنة مع العتبة المرجعية. علاوة على ذلك، بالمقارنة مع العتبة المرجعية، فإن إضافة تسليح GFRP أدى إلى زيادة الليونة بشكل كبير، حيث زادت بمقدار 1.0 إلى 2.20 مرة في المجموعة الأولى و 5.79 مرة في المجموعة الثانية.

في الدراسة، تراوحت نسبة الأحمال المحسوبة رقمياً إلى النتائج المختبرية للحمل النهائي والهطول النهائي من 0.90 إلى 1.06 ومن 1.0 إلى 1.11، على التوالي، عند مقارنة تنبؤات ABAQUS/Standard العناصر المحدودة (FE) بالنتائج التجريبية. وقد لوحظ انخفاض بنسبة 22% إلى 40% في قدرة التحميل النهائية عندما تم تخفيض نسبة GFRP إلى 2.235% و 1.257% على التوالي. تم تطبيق ثلاث نسب حديد تسليح مختلفة (3.492%، و 2.235%، و 1.257%) في تراكم UHPC، مما أدى إلى تعزيز خطي ثابت في Pu للعتبة بنسبة 134%، و 93%، و 57%، على التوالي، مقارنة مع العتبة المرجعية. بالإضافة إلى ذلك، عند إجراء المقارنة مع العتبة المقواة بطبقة UHPC العادية، زاد الحمل النهائي بنسبة 86% و 53%

و25% على التوالي. أدى استخدام قضبان البوليمر المسلح بألياف الكربون (CFRP) كتسليح لطبقة UHPC إلى زيادة كبيرة في الحمل النهائي مقارنة بالعتبات المقواة بطبقة UHPC المسلحة بـ GFRP.

في النهاية، أدى استخدام قوة ضغط الخرسانة العادية (NC) التي تتراوح من 20 ميغا باسكال إلى 60 ميغا باسكال إلى انخفاض بنسبة 5% وزيادة بنسبة 10% في سعة التحميل النهائية للعتبات الخرسانية المسلحة (RC)، على التوالي، بالمقارنة مع القيمة العملية 35 ميغا باسكال. عندما تم تقليل طول قضبان GFRP إلى 1500 مم (0.75 من الطول الصافي للعتبة)، انخفض الحمل النهائي بنسبة ضئيلة بنسبة 5% مقارنة بالعتبة المسلحة بقضبان GFRP بطول 2210 مم.

تم استخدام نموذج تحليلي لوضع مبادئ توجيهية للتصميم للتنبؤ بقدرة التحميل النهائية للعتبات التي تتضمن تقوية UHPC المسلحة بـ GFRP أظهرت المعادلة المطورة في قضبان البوليمر المسلح بالألياف الزجاجية تنبؤات دقيقة للحمل النهائي، حيث أظهرت قيمًا متوسطة قدرها 1.00 و0.97، مع انحرافات معيارية قدرها 0.05 و0.03، على التوالي، عند مقارنتها بالنتائج التجريبية ونتائج دراسة العناصر المحددة FE.

جمهورية العراق
وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي
جامعة بابل
كلية الهندسة
قسم الهندسة المدنية

سلوك العتبات الخرسانية المسلحة المقواة بواسطة طبقات
خرسانة فائقة الأداء والمسلحة بقضبان البوليمر المسلحة
بالألياف الزجاجية

رسالة

مقدمة إلى كلية الهندسة في جامعة بابل

كجزء من متطلبات نيل درجة الماجستير في علوم الهندسة/ الهندسة المدنية/ إنشاعات

من قبل

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بكالوريوس هندسة مدنية 2016

اشراف

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